

Grant Agreement No.: 101102718 Call: DIGITAL-2022-DEPLOY-02

Type of action: DIGITAL-CSA

SEEBLOCKS.eu

Supporting Europe's effort in Blockchain/DLT Standardisation

D4.9 Blockchain/DLT Standardisation Policy Roadmap (final)

Work package	WP4 "Outreach, education, and sustainability"
Task	T4.3
Due date (modified)	2025-05-31
Submission date	2025-05-30
Deliverable lead	Fraunhofer-Gesellschaft zur Förderung der angewandten Forschung e.V.
Version	V1.0
Authors	Simone Wurster and Knut Blind
Reviewers	John Favaro and Rita Meneses (Trust-IT)
Keywords	Blockchain, distributed ledgers, DLT, standards, roadmap

Document Revision History

Version	Date	Description of change	List of contributors
0.2	2025-01-07	Review of the roadmap's preliminary version (SEEBLOCKS D4.5) and beginning of writing	Simone Wurster
0.5	2025-04-30	Inclusion of implications from the ICT Rolling Plan 2025, SEEBLOCKS.eu's impact event and other strategically selected SEEBLOCKS.eu events to derive implications for the roadmap, inclusion of the section on education needs, adjustment of the table of content	Simone Wurster
0.7	2025-05-13	Additional inputs, completion of several updates after SEEBLOCKS.eu's strategy board meeting	Simone Wurster
0.8	2025-05-19	First Fraunhofer-internal update completed; first project-internal version provided	Simone Wurster, Knut Blind
0.9	2025-05-23	Inclusion of comments and suggestions by partners	John Favaro, Rita Meneses
1.0	2025-05-28	Version 1.0 of the document	Simone Wurster, Knut Blind

Disclaimer

SEEBLOCKS.eu has received funding from the European Union's Digital Europe Programme under Grant Agreement No. 101102718. The content of this document does not represent the opinion of the European Union, and the European Union is not responsible for any use that might be made of such content.

The European Commission is not liable for any use that may be made of the information contained herein.

Copyright notice

Dissemination Level		
PU	Public, fully open, e.g., web	✓
CO	Confidential, only for members of the consortium (including the Commission)	
EU-RES	Classified Information: RESTREINT UE (Commission Decision 2005/444/EC)	
EU-CON	Classified Information: CONFIDENTIEL UE (Commission Decision 2005/444/EC)	
EU-SEC	EU-SEC. Classified Information: SECRET UE (Commission Decision 2005/444/EC)	

* *R: Document, report (excluding the periodic and final reports)*

DEM: Demonstrator, pilot, prototype, plan designs

DEC: Websites, patents filing, press & media actions, videos, etc.

OTHER: Software, technical diagram, etc.

Executive Summary

This deliverable, issued at Month 24 of SEEBLOCKS.eu, is the second iteration of the project's Blockchain/Distributed Ledger Technologies (DLT) Standardisation Policy Roadmap. The roadmap has an international focus, provides a 5-year outlook and addresses eight topic areas:

- Artificial Intelligence (AI) Act;
- Data Act;
- General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR);
- Regulation on electronic identification and trust services (EUDI – eIDAS2);
- Decentralised Identifiers (DIDs) in Smart Contracts and beyond;
- Interoperability across territories;
- Smart Contracts;
- CO₂ footprint of blockchain.

This report provides the roadmap with its goals, action items, priorities and timelines. It also discusses gaps, barriers and countermeasures and is organised as follows:

- **Section 2** presents SEEBLOCKS.eu's research method, including a description of the fundamental roadmapping elements, their application to the project's framework conditions and in particular its public consultation;
- **Section 3** describes the current state in the eight areas of SEEBLOCKS.eu's analysis, concluding with a summary of key topics and players;
- **Section 4** shows the results of the public consultation, followed by the specification of the roadmap elements and
- **Section 5** provides a summary and outlook on the next steps after SEEBLOCKS.eu's completion.

Compared with the first edition of the Blockchain/DLT Standardisation Policy Roadmap, this updated document considers particularly the following additional aspects:

- Adjusted framework conditions based on the EU's ICT Rolling Plan 2025;
- Insights gained at the 2025 SES Annual Conference's SEEBLOCKS.eu workshop and in discussions with conference participants;
- Trends presented at the European Blockchain Standardisation Day, organised by SEEBLOCKS.eu and BlockStand on 9 April 2025;
- Experts' views presented at the SEEBLOCKS.eu Impact Event on 10 April 2025 and in additional individual communications with SEEBLOCKS.eu;
- Changes in the blockchain/DLT landscape according to SEEBLOCKS.eu deliverable D3.6;
- Results of discussions with SEEBLOCKS.eu's Strategy Board and Technical Working Group on the landscape report and the roadmap.

- Adjusted framework conditions regarding the collaboration with the United States.

The resulting changes include particularly an adjustment of the priorities related to cross-technology standardisation, specifically related to blockchain and AI. Likewise, the above-mentioned events emphasized the constant need for standardisation education. It has therefore been included in the roadmap as a permanent (short-, medium- and long-term) priority.

Based on latest developments, the recommendations regarding Decentralized Identifiers were also updated. Likewise, this updated roadmap considers the changing framework conditions in the relationship between the US and Europe and makes new proposals for their cooperation to strengthen the international blockchain ecosystem.

The needs for standardisation and policy measures shown in the next tables are key results of SEEBLOCKS.eu's public consultation and its review in the project's second project year. They are central action items of the Blockchain/DLT Standardisation Policy Roadmap. The topics are categorised according to short, medium and long-term priorities and assigned to the responsibility of various stakeholders.

Needs for standardisation¹:

Short-term priorities

1. Establish "Joining Forces for Blockchain Standardisation and Regulation" working groups that also have a specific focus on dialogues between both domains.
2. Develop a guiding standard for security, privacy and access that specifically considers the European requirements of the Digital Operational Resilience Act (DORA), GDPR, EU Digital Identity, eIDAS2.
3. Initiate the creation of a European standard framework for blockchain / DLT solution for EU Digital Identity Wallet (EUDIW).
4. Further work on SSI interoperability standardisation, specifically that a credential managed by EUDIW can be recognized by other Self-sovereign Identities (SSI) systems from other regions ("transatlantic" wallet interoperability).
5. Further work on Decentralised Identifier (DID) interoperability; initiate standardisation bridging DIDs and Blockchain / DLT beyond W3C's work by also considering the European specificities including the eIDAS2 regulation.¹
6. Work on the creation of signature standards on blockchains.
7. Initiate a CEN-CLC-ETSI Joint Working Group (JWG) on EBSI-related standardisation topics.

¹ All abbreviations are included in a dedicated section of this document after the list of figures.

8. Analyse suitable topics for further standardisation measures to support EBSI and initiate appropriate follow-up measures, analyse the needs for sector-specific standards related to EBSI specifically.
9. Further analyse standardisation needs related to Decentralized Public Key Infrastructure (DPKI) and implement appropriate follow-up measures.
10. Further check the needs for qualified Electronic Ledger certification guidelines.
11. Develop standards for audits and security metrics for smart contracts.
12. Initiate standardisation for blockchain Oracle programs.
13. Further analyse and address the needs for additional standards for data formats, data exchange and data portability according to current needs.
14. Develop a definition of what eco-sustainability means in the blockchain context.
15. Develop standards for environmental and innovation management of DLTs to support the industry competitiveness and sustainable growth and ensure sustainability and safety for consumers, develop standards towards assessing environmental and sustainability impact including, in particular, CO₂ footprint and energy consumption of different blockchains/DLTs, markets in crypto-assets (MiCA), EU Sustainable Finance taxonomy.²
16. Develop standards and technical guidelines for blockchain-supported trusted AI.

Medium-term priorities

1. Care for additional needs regarding data formats and data exchange according to the short-term analysis.
2. Further analyses of standardisation opportunities regarding an erasable second blockchain/DLT layer.

Long-term priorities

1. Needs for additional cross-technology standardisation topics in the blockchain context with specific consideration of ethical aspects

Not specified

1. Analyse potential needs for supplementary standardisation work to support the work of the international Financial Action Task Force (FATF).

¹ Already some progress at the time of finalising this roadmap, combined with the identification of further specifying action items.

² Updated priority based on the ICT Rolling Plan 2025, replacing the sustainability priority of this report's first version, which is already considered by the time of this report's completion: "Develop standards to calculate the CO₂ footprint per transaction (if not yet addressed by the time of this roadmap's implementation)". The recommendation of the roadmap's first version "Based on the need for a definition described above, check which additional sustainability aspects need further standardisation" was also integrated into this action item.

Needs for policy-based support:

Short-term priorities

1. Join the standards community in establishing “Joining Forces for Blockchain Standardisation and Regulation” working groups that also have a specific focus on dialogues between standardisation and regulation.
2. Specify requirements for legal validity and enforceability of **Smart Contracts**, further analyse additional needs regarding the legal recognition of DLTs and DLT-based solutions.
3. Develop **DID policies** and create suitable regulatory framework conditions to support the interoperability between DIDs.
4. Support education on blockchain standardisation also considering the international workshop agreement IWA 30-1 on competencies of standards professionals in companies

Medium-term priorities

1. Provide suitable regulatory framework conditions for blockchain governance by considering the suggested guiding standards for security, privacy and access that specifically consider the European requirements of DORA, GDPR, EU Digital Identity, eIDAS2.
2. Further care for **trusted registries**: further analyse the needs for regulatory support and improvements in the regulatory framework conditions.
3. Check needs for additional regulatory measures for **Decentralised Finance** besides the international FATF regulation.
4. Specify the **sustainability framework** for blockchain including acceptable CO₂ footprints and rules for covering environmental cost.
5. Specify standardisation education by also considering the final results of the EDU4Standards.eu project and analyse updated education needs.

Long-term priorities

1. Adjust blockchain and ICT standardisation education strategies, e.g. within the project StandICT 2029.

Variable priority

1. Check the feasibility of extending the **EU Copyright Directive**, addressing blockchain/DLT-based opportunities to contribute to copyright protection.

Table of Contents

1.	Introduction	13
2.	Method	16
2.1	Roadmapping elements.....	16
2.2	Overview of SEEBLOCKS.eu’s roadmapping activities for the year 1 edition and preliminary research in the key roadmap areas.....	17
2.3	SEEBLOCKS.eu’s public consultation.....	18
2.3.1	Elements	18
2.3.2	Consultation process and participants	19
2.3.3	Additional methods for the year 2 edition	20
3.	Current state in the key roadmap areas.....	21
3.1	Current state in standardisation.....	21
3.2	Relevant regulations	23
3.2.1	Data Act	23
3.2.2	General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR)	24
3.2.3	Regulation on electronic identification & trust services (EUDI, eIDAS2)	25
3.2.4	Artificial Intelligence Act.....	26
3.3	Interoperability across territories.....	27
3.4	Smart Contracts	29
3.5	Decentralised Identifiers (DIDs) in Smart Contracts and beyond.....	30
3.6	CO ₂ footprint of blockchain	31
3.7	Roadmap topics based on the preliminary analysis	33
4.	Roadmap elements.....	38
4.1	Building blocks based on SEEBLOCKS.eu’s public consultation.....	38
4.1.1	Action items regarding data exchange, electronic identification & trust services, DIDs, Smart Contracts, data protection & AI.....	38
4.1.2	Specific action items related to interoperability	39
4.1.3	Short, medium and long-term standardisation priorities	42

4.2	Overview of the roadmap elements.....	43
4.3	Standardisation education as overarching priority	45
4.4	Short-term priorities.....	46
4.4.1	Creation of “Joining Forces for Blockchain Standardisation and Regulation” working groups as fundamental action item.....	46
4.4.2	Interoperability and data formats	48
4.4.3	Electronic identification and trust services	50
4.4.4	Decentralised Identity	51
4.4.5	Smart Contract security	53
4.4.6	Environmental sustainability and CO ₂ footprint.....	53
4.4.7	Artificial Intelligence and blockchain.....	55
4.5	Medium-term priorities.....	58
4.5.1	Additional data exchange topics	58
4.5.2	Governance policies to support interoperability	58
4.5.3	Data protection.....	59
4.6	Long-term priorities.....	60
4.7	Additional standardisation and policy topics	60
4.8	Key players for the roadmap’s implementation.....	61
4.9	Potential barriers and gaps in the implementation of the roadmap and reaction measures.....	64
5.	Summary and next steps	67
5.1	Roadmap priorities regarding standardisation.....	67
5.2	Roadmap priorities for policy support.....	70
5.3	Current impact of SEEBLOCKS.eu’s roadmap and outlook.....	72
	Annex 1: Roadmap Questionnaire of the Open Consultation	80
	Annex 2: Answers of the Open Consultation.....	84
	Interoperability problems of blockchain/DLT between the EU, the U.S. and Asia that could be addressed by standardisation	84
	Various suggestions for regulatory measures or standardisation to support blockchain interoperability	85

General suggestions regarding the short-, medium- & long-term priorities.....	87
Specific recommendations related to identification & trusted services	91
Specific recommendations related to Decentralised Identifiers (DIDs)	92
Specific recommendations related to data exchange	93
Specific recommendations related to the CO ₂ footprint	94
Specific recommendations related to data protection and the GDPR	95
Specific recommendations related to AI.....	96
Suggestions for additional regulatory/policy support	97

List of Figures

Figure 1: European policy objectives for Distributed Ledgers Technologies	14
Figure 2: Elements of SEEBLOCKS.eu's roadmap development	16
Figure 3: Current state of Blockchain/DLT specifications by topic: formal standards and specifications of industry organisations	21
Figure 4: Recommendations of the CEN-CENELEC focus group on blockchain/DLT regarding the GDPR	24
Figure 5: Needs for standards and/or regulations in selected areas to support blockchain/ DLT	38
Figure 6: Ranking of action items related to interoperability	39
Figure 7: Perception of interoperability problems between the EU, the U.S. and Asia that could be addressed by standardisation	41
Figure 8: Short, medium & long-term standardisation priorities beyond the key data exchange & interoperability topics.....	42
Figure 9: Additional voices related to SEEBLOCKS' impact event's topic Trusted AI: excerpts of a Bundesblock position paper	57
Figure 10: Overview of the ICT Rolling Plan.....	73
Figure 11: Important dates of the EU's ICT Rolling Plan 2026.....	74

List of Tables

Table 1: Topic areas of the standardisation policy roadmap	14
Table 2: Standardisation groups analysed by Fardad et al. (2024) and in Figure 3.....	22
Table 3: Key SDOs for the roadmap topics	33
Table 4: Roadmap topics based on the preliminary analysis	31
Table 5: Short, medium and long-term priorities for standardisation and policies to support for blockchain/DLT.....	44
Table 6: Priorities and suggested responsibilities	62
Table 7: Potential barriers and gaps in the implementation of the roadmap and reaction measures.....	65
Table 8: Short, medium & long-term priorities for standardisation and policies to support blockchain & DLT according to Table 5.....	68

Abbreviations

Acronym	Description
AhG	Ad hoc group
AI	artificial intelligence
AIOTI	Alliance for IoT and Edge Computing Innovation
ANSI	American National Standards Institute
ARF	Architecture and Reference Framework
BNDES	Brazilian Development Bank
CBDC	Central Bank Digital Currency
CEN	European Committee for Standardization
CENELEC, CLC	European Committee for Electrotechnical Standardization
CRA	EU Cyber Resilience Act
DCU	Dublin City University
DID	Decentralised Identifier
DIN	Deutsches Institut für Normung e. V.
DLT	Distributed Ledger Technologies
DORA	Digital Operational Resilience Act
DPKI	Decentralized Public Key Infrastructure
EBP	European Blockchain Partnership
EBSI	European Blockchain Services Infrastructure
EEA	Enterprise Ethereum Alliance
eIDAS	Electronic Identification, Authentication and Trust Services
ESI	Electronic Signatures and Trust Infrastructures
ESO	European standardisation organisation
ETSI	European Telecommunications Standards Institute
EU	European Union
EUDI	European Digital Identity
EUDIW	EU Digital Identity Wallet
EUOS	EU Observatory for ICT Standardisation
FATF	Financial Action Task Force
FSRA	Financial Services Regulatory Authority
GBBC	Global Blockchain Business Council
GDPR	General Data Protection Regulation
GS	Group Specification
GT	Group Report
IEA	International Energy Agency
IEEE	Institute of Electrical and Electronics Engineers

Acronym	Description
IETF	Internet Engineering Task Force
IMPULSE	Identity Management in PUBlic Services
IoT	Internet of Things
IRTF	Internet Research Task Force
ISG	Industry Specification Group(s)
ISO	International Standards Organization
ITSA	International Token Standardization Association
ITU	International Telecommunication Union
ITU-T	ITU Telecommunication Standardization Sector
IWA	International Workshop Agreement
JTC	Joint Technical Committee
JWG	Joint Working Group
MiCA	markets in crypto-assets
MSP	European multi-stakeholder platform on ICT standardisation
NIST	National Institute of Standards and Technology
NSB	National Standardisation Body
PDL	Permissioned distributed ledgers
OCG AI	Operational Coordination Group for AI
SAI	Securing Artificial Intelligence
SDO	Standards development organisation
SEP	Selection and Engagement Procedure
SSI	Self-sovereign Identities (Note: in other contexts, SEEBLOCKS.eu also uses SSI for "Specifically-Supported Initiates")
StandICT	ICT Standardisation Observatory and Support Facility in Europe
SWIFT	Society for Worldwide Interbank Financial Telecommunication
TC	Technical Committee
TR	Technical Report
Trust-IT	Trust-IT Srl
UNE	Asociación Española de Normalización
W3C	World Wide Web Consortium
WG	Working Group
WP	Work package
ZKP	zero-knowledge proof

1. Introduction

Standardisation and standards are significant drivers for economic growth² and also recognized instruments to address specific economic challenges. Increased economic and system competition puts the EU and also its values under pressure. These significant current changes in the geopolitical environment call for not only keeping the current but even having a stronger EU presence in international standardisation committees (see European Commission, 2022).

Focusing on blockchain is an important aspect in this context. Blockchain “has great potential in providing an infrastructure for trusted, decentralised and disintermediated services beyond the financial sector. While the FinTech industry has been an early adopter because of its early use case of Bitcoin, blockchain (...) has the potential to transform many other industries. It is considered a foundational technology that some compare to the rise of the Internet in the early 90s” (European Commission, 2025).

The European Commission's Blockchain Strategy (European Commission, 2023) under the responsibility of the Directorate-General for Communications Networks, Content and Technology (DG CONNECT) is designed to meet these goals, particularly in terms of trust, transparency, and decentralization (see European Commission, 2023a). For this reason, DG CONNECT is also one of the key addressees of this roadmap, together with the European standardisation organisations (ESOs).

An important initiative in this context is the European Multi-Stakeholder Platform on ICT Standardisation (MSP), which is chaired by DG CONNECT³. It was set up following a Commission Decision to advise on all matters related to the implementation of ICT standardisation policies. One of its key initiatives is the Rolling Plan for ICT standardisation (in the following ICT Rolling Plan) and the specification of its annual editions. The ICT Rolling Plan outlines activities that connect EU policies to standardisation efforts in more than 30 technological domains. One of these domains is Blockchain and Distributed Digital Ledger Technologies, for which SEEBLOCKS.eu has created specific input, presented in this report.⁴

A specific framework condition of SEEBLOCKS.eu's work is set by the European Commission's policy objectives for Distributed Ledgers Technologies, summarized in Figure 1.

As written in SEEBLOCKS.eu's Grant Agreement, the roadmap is produced with support from the experts engaged during the project duration and aims to direct future efforts of reinforcing European values, ethics and policies in eight topic areas shown in Table 1.

² Fundamental sources of this section: ISO (2021); Blind & Heß (2023); Swann (2010); Edler, et al. (2023); Blind & von Laer, (2022), Blind et al. (2022); Blind, et al. (2018); Blind & Gauch (2009).

³ Link: <https://digital-strategy.ec.europa.eu/en/policies/multi-stakeholder-platform-ict-standardisation>

⁴ Unless otherwise stated, all references to the Rolling Plan in this report refer to the Blockchain/DLT chapter.

Source: SEEBLOCKS.eu based on external European sources

Figure 1: European policy objectives for Distributed Ledgers Technologies

Topic areas of the standardisation policy roadmap
Regulation on electronic identification and trust services (EUDI – eIDAS2)
General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR)
Data Act
Artificial Intelligence Act
Interoperability across territories (US, Australia, etc.)
Smart Contracts
Decentralised Identifiers (DIDs) in Smart Contracts and beyond
CO ₂ footprint of blockchain

Table 1: Topic areas of the standardisation policy roadmap

The roadmap has a 5-year outlook and an international dimension.

According to IEA (2014), the development of roadmaps relies on five elements: goals, milestones, gaps and barriers, action items, priorities and timelines, which is reflected in this report.

Compared to its first version, it specifically emphasizes cross-technology standardisation, in particular related to blockchain and artificial intelligence (AI). In line with the consideration of AI-specific implications of the ICT Rolling Plan 2025, it also reflects the view of several pioneers of SEEBLOCKS.eu's open consultation, who unlike the majority, already categorized AI and blockchain as a short-term standardisation priority.

As an additional update, the ICT Rolling Plan 2025 specified its action item to develop standards and technical guidance for environmental and innovation management of DLTs to support the industry competitiveness and sustainable growth and ensure sustainability is considered. This consideration replaces a recommendation of the first version of this roadmap regarding the CO₂ footprint of blockchain, for which several preparatory standardisation measures have already started.

To fulfil the technical goals of the ICT Rolling Plan, the roadmap also specifies short-, medium- and long-term measures for education on blockchain standardisation.

This updated roadmap also considers the changing framework conditions in the relationship between the US and Europe and makes new proposals for their cooperation to strengthen the international blockchain ecosystem.

As a starting point of the roadmap development, the current state of the regulatory and standardisation frameworks of SEEBLOCKS.eu's eight topic areas is presented in chapter 3. It follows the description of the methods applied for the creation of this report in the next chapter.

2. Method

2.1 Roadmapping elements

According to IEA (2014, p.5), which is the foundation of this section, and Figure 2, the development of roadmaps relies in five elements: goals, milestones, gaps and barriers, action items and priorities and timelines.

Figure 2: Elements of SEEBLOCKS.eu's roadmap development

Goals are defined as a clear and concise set of targets that, if achieved, will result in the desired outcome.

Milestones are the interim performance targets for achieving the goals, pegged to specific dates.

Gaps and barriers refer to a list of any potential gaps in knowledge, technology limitations, market structural barriers, regulatory limitations, public acceptance or other barriers to achieving the goals and milestones.

Action items are actions that can be taken to achieve the roadmap's goals. Typical actions include technology development and deployment, development of regulations and standards, policy formulation, creation of financing mechanisms, and public engagement.

Priorities and timelines mean a list of the most important actions that need to be taken to achieve the goals and the time frames, taking into account interconnections among those actions and stakeholder roles and relationships.

SEEBLOCKS's specific roadmapping activities are described in the next section.

2.2 Overview of SEEBLOCKS.eu's roadmapping activities for the year 1 edition and preliminary research in the key roadmap areas

According to Figure 2, the development of roadmaps relies on five elements: goals, milestones, gaps and barriers, action items and priorities and timelines.

This Blockchain/DLT Standardisation Policy Roadmap aims to support blockchain technology in fully unleashing its potential to revolutionise information sharing and online transactions. Its specific goal is to supplement the European Commission's Blockchain Strategy's (European Commission, 2023a) current measures to meet these goals.

Eight topic areas, for which this roadmap should give guidance were specified according to Table 1: 1. Regulation on electronic identification and trust services (EUDI – eIDAS2), 2. General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR), 3. Data Act, 4. Artificial Intelligence Act, 5. Interoperability across territories (US, Australia, etc.), 6. Smart Contracts, 7. Decentralised Identifiers (DIDs) in Smart Contracts and beyond, 8. CO₂ footprint of blockchain.

The specification of topic-specific goals started with the analysis of the topic areas' current state. Important sources in this context included SEEBLOCKS Landscape Reports (Delaney et al., 2023 and Fardad et al., 2024) and the material collected for SEEBLOCKS.eu's visualization tool.⁵ Key sources regarding already specified goals related to the roadmap's eight topic areas included in particular the Blockchain chapter of the ICT Rolling Plan 2024 and the project's first public consultation (Delaney et al., 2024). Additional important sources included the reports of SEEBLOCKS.eu's SEP (Selection and Engagement Procedure) projects and information exchanges with the experts of SEEBLOCKS.eu's webinars and past and current projects such as Trace4EU⁶ and the former IMPULSE⁷ project.

The results of SEEBLOCKS.eu's first public consultation on the future of Blockchain and DLT in general emphasized the importance of the following topics:

- Governance models to enable interoperability across the tech stack (Cloud Computing, Peer to Peer computing, Edge and fog computing);
- Standards for data formats and Interoperability (eIDAS2, SWIFT);
- Guidelines for security, privacy and access (DORA, GDPR, EU Digital Identity, eIDAS2).

Combining the research needs in the roadmap's eight topic areas with these first implications, we included a dedicated section on SEEBLOCKS.eu's roadmap in SEEBLOCKS.eu's second public

⁵ Link: <https://seeblocks.eu/visualisation-tool>

⁶ Link: <https://trace4eu.eu/>

⁷ Identity Management in Public Services, link: <https://www.impulse-h2020.eu/>

consultation, addressing all eight topic areas in six theme clusters. The consultation will be described in detail in section 2.3.

2.3 SEEBLOCKS.eu's public consultation

2.3.1 Elements

An important part of SEEBLOCKS.eu is a public consultation on future blockchain-related standardisation topics important for European interests and values.

A freely accessible section is provided on the project website to spark conversation on any Blockchain/DLT related subject for users and experts. Two public consultations on Blockchain/DLT standardisation aim to receive insights from all stakeholders. The open public consultations are carried out online and follow a rigorous cycle to reflect on relevant stakeholders' positions, maintain inclusivity, and guarantee European interests are considered. A sub-committee of the project's Strategy Board supervises the consultation process.

Besides statistical questions, SEEBLOCKS.eu's public consultation used for the development of this roadmap had six key roadmapping topics. They are summarised below and shown in detail in Annex 1.

The **first roadmapping** set of questions referred to the classification of eight blockchain and adjacent standardisation topics as short, medium and long-term priorities:

- Interoperability between different blockchain networks;
- Smart contract security;
- Artificial Intelligence and blockchain (e.g., governance and transparency layer on DLT);
- CO₂ footprint of blockchain and other high-compute services (e.g., Quantum computing, Training AI models);
- Data exchange (e.g., eIDAS2, SWIFT);
- Data protection (e.g., GDPR, EU AI Act);
- Electronic identification and trust services (e.g., related to EUDI – eIDAS2);
- Decentralised Identity (e.g., Self-sovereign Identities (SSI), DID, eIDAS2).

The classification was followed by a specification of the standardisation needs.

The **second topic** was a ranking of the interoperability action items and an analysis of potential interoperability problems of blockchain/DLT between the EU, the U.S. and Asia that could be

addressed by standardisation. In addition, potential additional measures that should be undertaken by regulation (law) or voluntary standardisation to support the interoperability of blockchain/DLT were discussed.

The **third topic** referred to specific blockchain-related standardisation needs in relation to data protection and Europe's General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR).

The **fourth topic** was a potential need for specific blockchain-related AI (artificial intelligence) standards or regulation.

The **fifth topic** was a detailed analysis of needs for standards and/or regulations in the following areas to support blockchain/DLT:

- CO₂ footprint of blockchain;
- Data exchange;
- Electronic identification and trust services (EUDI – eIDAS2);
- Decentralised Identifiers (DIDs) in Smart Contracts and beyond.

The **sixth topic** referred to needs for additional regulatory/policy support for blockchain/DLT technologies.

2.3.2 Consultation process and participants

The public consultation for the fundamental work on SEEBLOCKS.eu's roadmap took place between July 1 and September 15, 2024.

26 experts from 14 countries participated in the consultation while most participants came from Italy (5 participants), Germany (4 participants) and Spain (3 participants). The proportion of women was 20% and 80% were male participants.

Participants' most frequent organisation type was academia (8 participants), followed by Start-Ups, Small and Medium Enterprises (7 participants) and Associations & Non-Profit Organisations (4 participants).

More details on SEEBLOCKS.eu's second public consultation as a whole, lasting until October 4, 2024 are provided by SEEBLOCKS.eu's deliverable D3.5 Report of results of the second-iteration public consultation.

2.3.3 Additional methods for the year 2 edition

Compared with the first edition of the Blockchain/DLT Standardisation Policy Roadmap, this document considers particularly the following additional aspects:

- Adjusted framework conditions based on the EU's ICT Rolling Plan 2025;
- Insights gained at the 2025 SES Annual Conference's SEEBLOCKS.eu workshop and in discussions with conference participants;
- Trends presented at the European Blockchain Standardisation Day, organised by SEEBLOCKS.eu and BlockStand on 9 April 2025;
- Experts' views presented at the SEEBLOCKS.eu Impact Event on 10 April 2025 and in additional individual communication with SEEBLOCKS.eu;
- Changes in the blockchain/DLT landscape according to SEEBLOCKS.eu deliverable D3.6;
- Results of discussions with SEEBLOCKS.eu's Strategy Board and Technical Working Group on the landscape report and the roadmap
- Adjusted framework conditions regarding the collaboration with the United States.

The resulting changes include particularly an adjustment of the priorities related to cross-technology standardisation, specifically related to blockchain and AI.

Ongoing activities regarding the environmental sustainability of blockchain and the ICT Rolling Plan's latest action in this context were also specifically considered.

Likewise, the above-mentioned events emphasized the need of standardisation education. Therefore, we included it as a short-, medium- and long-term priority.

This updated roadmap also considers the evolving framework of US-Europe relations and proposes new measures to enhance their cooperation in strengthening the international blockchain ecosystem.

3. Current state in the key roadmap areas

3.1 Current state in standardisation

This chapter describes the current state of blockchain/DLT standardisation regarding SEEBLOCKS.eu eight priority areas. Key sources included:

- SEEBLOCKS.eu report D3.1 Blockchain and DLT standardisation landscape report (Delaney, 2023);
- SEEBLOCKS.eu report D3.2 Report of results of the early public consultation (Delaney et al., 2024);
- SEEBLOCKS.eu report Landscape and gap analysis report on Blockchain/DLT standardisation – Mid-term rel. (D3.3, Fardad et al., 2024) and final release (D3.6, SEEBLOCKS.eu (2025), forthcoming);
- The ICT Rolling Plan 2024 and 2025 (European Commission, 2024a,b, 2025).

and additional own analyses. The current blockchain/DLT standardisation landscape is visualised in Figure 2.

Source: SEEBLOCKS.eu partner DCU, figure kindly created for this report, consideration of 116 standards

Note: The figure represents the standards distribution per level 1 criteria according to the INATBA method (INATBA, 2024). The organisations, also including industry standards organisations, whose work was analysed include ISO, ITU-T, IEEE, CEN/CENELEC, ETSI, ANSI, NIST, UNE, DIN, ITSA, IETF and EEA

Figure 3: Current state of Blockchain/DLT specifications by topic: formal standards and specifications of industry organisations

An earlier version of this figure was also presented in Fardad et al. (2024). While their analysis relied on the identification of 97 standards in the areas shown in Figure 2, the current number is 116, showing that almost 20 additional standards have been created in these areas in the meantime. The increase was particularly driven by new standards in the fields of governance, security and technology.

As Figure 3 shows specifically, foundations for the work in the topic areas are laid already. Interoperability and Smart Contracts for example, are explicitly mentioned as a specific standards group. However, no additional standards in these areas were reported after the analysis conducted in Fardad et al. (2024). Detailed information on the standardisation groups whose work was considered is provided by Table 2.

SDO	Organisation type	Committee/ Group	Focus Area
ISO	International	ISO/TC 307	DLT Standardisation
ITU-T	International	TSAG	DLT, ICT
IEEE	International	CTS/BSC, C/BDL, BOG/CAG, CTS/DFESC, IES/IES, PE/SBLC, C/SAB, EMB/StdCom	Blockchain, DLT, Consumer Technology, Digital Finance, Industrial Electronics, Smart Buildings
CEN/CENELEC	European	JTC 19, WG 01	Decentralised Identity Management
ETSI	European	ISG PDL, IPv6 groups	Permissioned Distributed Ledger, IPv6
ANSI	National	ASC X9, X9A	DLT Terminology, Blockchain Risk Assessment
NIST	National	CSD, ACD	Blockchain Security, Cybersecurity
UNE	National	SC 307	Blockchain and DLT
DIN	National	NA 043-0204 AA, NA 009-00-15-02 AK	DLT Specifications, Records Management
Industry standards organisation	Organisation type	Committee/ Group	Focus Area
ITSA	Industry	PWG1, PWG2, PWG3	Token Standardisation, Token Identification, Token Classification, Token Analysis
IETF	Industry	Secure Asset Transfer Protocol WG	Secure Asset Transfer, Cross-Network Asset Transfer
EEA	Industry	Six active Working Groups	Enterprise Ethereum, Blockchain Leaders, Adopters, Innovators, Developers, Businesses

Source: Fardad et al. (2024), modified and shortened. Please visit the websites of the organisations concerned for the detailed names of the specific committees

Table 2: Standardisation groups analysed by Fardad et al. (2024) and in Figure 3

On the international and Pan-European level they include the International Organization for Standardization (ISO), the ITU Telecommunication Standardization Sector (ITU-T), the European Committee for Standardisation (CEN), the European Committee for Electrotechnical Standardization (CENELEC) and European Telecommunications Standards Institute (ETSI).

The analysis also considered the work of the United States' key standardisation players, the American National Standards Institute (ANSI) and the National Institute of Standards and Technology (NIST). With regards to the work on the level of the European member states, it presents the work of the Asociación Española de Normalización (UNE) and Germany's Deutsches Institut für Normung (DIN). In addition, their analysis considers the work of four Industry standards organizations and consortia: the Institute of Electrical and Electronics Engineers (IEEE), the International Token Standardization Association (ITSA), the Internet Engineering Task Force (IETF), and the Enterprise Ethereum Alliance (EEA).

The next subsections will provide additional insight in our focus areas. In this context, they will also show the importance of other organisations and groups, for example, of the World Wide Web Consortium (W3C), which was not part of Fardad et al.'s (2024) analysis. Although the W3C does not present itself as a specific blockchain-related standard-setter, its work is important in many blockchain-related technology areas.

According to its website,⁸ the W3C is an international public-interest non-profit organization with member organizations and currently 43 working groups. It was founded by the Web inventor Tim Berners-Lee and has the mission to lead the web to its full potential. In 2022 it presented strategic highlights and lists 1,149 standards. While searches for the "term blockchain" do not lead to results in these contexts, W3C informs about a liaison with the Accord Project regarding verifiable claims and Blockchain. In addition, the W3C is very active in the area of digital identifiers, which section 2 will explain in more detail.

Updates in the standardisation landscape observed by the time of this final version of the Blockchain/DLT Standardisation Policy Roadmap are presented in SEEBLOCKS.eu (2025).

3.2 Relevant regulations

3.2.1 Data Act

The **Regulation (EU) 2023/2854** of 13 December 2023 on harmonised rules on fair access to and use of data (Data Act (European Parliament and the Council, 2023b) established important frame-

⁸ <https://www.w3.org>

work conditions for further regulatory and standardisation-related measures. Its Article 36 describes “Essential requirements regarding Smart Contracts for executing data sharing agreements”⁹.

Regarding standardisation, in particular **ETSI** has become active. It aims to create an open ecosystem of industrial permissioned distributed ledgers (PDL) solutions supported by global, open telecommunications networks via its Industry Specification Group “Permissioned distributed ledgers” (**ISG PDL**). It is collaborating with ETSI TC ESI on eIDAS and in support of Smart Contracts in the Data Act context. In addition, ETSI’s TC on **Electronic Signatures and Trust Infrastructures (ESI)** aims to develop standards to support the data act.

The ICT Rolling Plan 2024 and 2025 include the following action regarding the Data Act: **2024’s Action 7/2025’s Action 6: ESOs to develop standards in line with the Data Act (...), in particular regarding essential requirements for smart-contracts.”**

3.2.2 General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR)

Fundamental work regarding the interplay of blockchain/DLT and the GDPR has been done by **CEN and CENELEC**. They established a **Focus Group** on Blockchain and DLT to identify specific European standardisation needs and to map them with the current work items in ISO/TC 307 Blockchain and distributed ledger technologies and to encourage further European participation there. Its report “Recommendations for Successful Adoption in Europe of Emerging Technical Standards on Distributed Ledger/Blockchain Technologies” considers the GDPR particularly in the chapter “Privacy and Data Protection”.¹⁰ The recommendations shown in Figure 4 were formulated.

- 1: It is fundamental that standardization efforts include the implications of GDPR within their related groups.
- 2: Defining and formulating GDPR compliant standards (e.g. in terms of design, architecture, non-reversible data transformation methods or address obfuscation methods) would have to consider impact on entrepreneurs and institutions.
- 3: Blockchain technology in relation to governance must address the data controller requirements of GDPR.

Figure 4: Recommendations of the CEN-CENELEC focus group on blockchain/DLT regarding the GDPR

⁹ See https://www.eu-data-act.com/Data_Act_Article_36.html

¹⁰ https://www.cencenelec.eu/media/CEN-CENELEC/Areas%20of%20Work/CEN%20sectors/Digital%20Society/Emerging%20technologies/fg-bDLT-white_paper-version1-2.pdf

The **ICT Rolling Plans 2024 and 2025** consider the GDPR by 2024's **Action 3/2025's Action 2**: "Continue identifying use cases which are relevant for EU (including EU regulatory requirements (...) from GDPR (...)) and submit them to relevant standardisation bodies, including CEN & CENELEC and ETSI, and also ISO, ITU."

Regarding activities on the national level, important work has been done at Germany's standardisation body **DIN**. An already existing document is **DIN SPEC 4997:2020-04**, developed at the German DIN and titled in English "Privacy by Blockchain Design: A standardised model for processing personal data using blockchain technology". According to its section 1, this specification establishes:

"(G)eneral principles for and methods of handling personal data in BC/DLT-systems. It specifies (...) measures for data protection while taking into account the principles of "privacy by design" as well as specifications that are inspired by legal frameworks, such as the GDPR. The document defines relevant terms (...) and establishes a methodological framework that helps to identify types of data (...) as well as mapping legal principles of the GDPR to technical measures available to improve data protection or mitigate the risk of processing personal data in BC/DLT-systems."

In line with the objectives of the ICT Rolling Plan, further developments towards a European specification appear to be worth analysing.

3.2.3 Regulation on electronic identification & trust services (EUDI, eIDAS2)

A key document on the European Digital Identity (EUDI) and eIDAS2 is **Regulation (EU) 2024/1183** of the European Parliament and of the Council of 11 April 2024 amending Regulation (EU) No 910/2014 as regards establishing the European Digital Identity Framework.

Its article 45 introduces European Digital Identity Wallets and qualified trust services for electronic ledgers.

A key EUDI activity refers to the European Digital Identity Wallet Architecture and Reference Framework.

In 2021, the European Commission adopted a Recommendation addressing the Member States to develop a common Union Toolbox for a coordinated approach towards a European Digital Identity Framework. As outlined in its introduction, this concept includes a technical Architecture and Reference Framework (ARF), a set of common standards and technical specifications and a set of common guidelines and best practices (see European Commission, 2021).

As highlighted by EUDI Wallet (2024), these outcomes will serve as a basis for the implementation of the European Digital Identity Framework.

The Recommendation specifies a structured cooperation process of Member States, the European Commission and, optionally, private sector operators, to develop the Toolbox. The eIDAS Expert Group is entrusted with the role of the main interlocutor to implement this Recommendation.

The eIDAS Expert Group has since further developed the concepts and specifications for the European Digital Identity Framework. The current ARF version 1.4.0 is based on the legal text adopted by the co-legislators, see EUDI Wallet (2024).

A key player on the side of SDOs in the EUDI/eIDAS2 context is **CEN-CENELEC's Focus Group** on Blockchain and Distributed Ledger Technologies that analyses standardisation needs in the context of eIDAS.

Regarding future measures, the **ICT Rolling Plan 2024's Action 3/2025's Action 2** mentioned before also highlights the need to continue identifying use cases regarding EU regulatory requirements related to ePrivacy and eIDAS and to submit them to relevant standardisation bodies.

Specific requirements for the future are also formulated by BITKOM (2023). In particular in the business-to-business sector, an international perspective beyond eIDAS 2.0 must be included in the governance of SSI (Self-sovereign identifiers). SSI offers interesting opportunities to think about security features in new ways, but also brings challenges. According to BITKOM (2023), there is also the question of internationally interoperable systems, beyond eIDAS (see section 3.3 of this report).

3.2.4 Artificial Intelligence Act

To specify the framework conditions for AI in Europe, the EU Artificial Intelligence Act was finally confirmed on 21 May 2024 and went into effect on August 1, 2024.

Various strategic standardisation plans and initiatives already take AI into account. The EU's current ICT Rolling Plan (European Commission, 2024a), for example, considers AI in a separate section, see European Commission (2024b). Specific initiatives listed in that plan include:

- CEN-CENELEC activities, in particular:
 - Focus Group on AI that created a roadmap for AI standardisation;
 - CEN-CENELEC's Joint Technical Committee CEN-CENELEC JTC 21 (see below).
- ETSI's activities in various technical bodies¹¹, in particular:

¹¹ See <https://portal.etsi.org/TB-SiteMap/OCG/OCG-AI-Co-ordination>

- ETSI Operational Coordination Group for AI (OCG AI)¹²;
- ETSI TC Securing Artificial Intelligence (SAI), formerly ETSI Industry Specification Groups (ISG) SAI.

In May 2023, the European Commission issued a first standardisation request to elaborate AI-related standards.¹³ In response, **CEN-CENELEC JTC 21** developed a work programme listing international and European standards that can support the Standardisation Request.

The **CEN-CENELEC Focus Group Road Map** on Artificial Intelligence has already considered an AI use case on blockchain.¹⁴

The **ICT Rolling Plan 2024** (European Commission, 2024b) included six AI-related actions in a specific AI chapter. Besides this, SEEBLOCKS saw a need to check with its stakeholders to what extent additional blockchain-related measures might be necessary.

In addition, both, the **2024 and the 2025 edition** of the Rolling Plan highlight that “we will see increased activity on standardisation for AI in the years to come, which will continue to be reflected in the Rolling Plan.” This development was also visible in our blockchain-related market observation in the last months. As we will show later, the updated edition of this roadmap increased the importance of standardisation related to blockchain-based trusted AI.

3.3 Interoperability across territories

In June 2020, the European Commission and INATBA, the International Association of Trusted Blockchain Applications, organised the webinar “Joining Forces for Blockchain Standardisation” (European Commission and INATBA, 2022). It included:

- Presentations of standardisation and technical specification bodies of ISO/TC 307 and its Joint Working Group (JWG) 4: Security privacy and identity for Blockchain and DLT, ITU-T, CEN-CENELEC JTC19, ETSI ISG PDL, IEEE Blockchain Standardisation, W3C, OASIS, IRTF/IETF;
- Presentations of the national & regional Initiatives of Australia, Japan, South Korea, India, UAE, Canada, Brazil, EUOS/StandICT, GBBC, AIOTI, LACChain and EBP/EBSI;

¹² See also <https://www.etsi.org/images/files/ETSIWhitePapers/ETSI-WP52-ETSI-activities-in-the-field-of-AI-B.pdf>

¹³ See [https://ec.europa.eu/transparency/documents-register/detail?ref=C\(2023\)3215&lang=en](https://ec.europa.eu/transparency/documents-register/detail?ref=C(2023)3215&lang=en)

¹⁴ See https://www.cenelec.eu/media/CEN-CENELEC/AreasOfWork/CEN-CENELEC_Topics/Artificial%20Intelligence/Quicklinks%20General/Documentation%20and%20Materials/cen-clc_fgreport_roadmap_ai.pdf

- Panellists of the European Blockchain Service Infrastructure, the IEEE Blockchain Initiative, the European Blockchain Center, BNDES, and UAE's Financial Services Regulatory Authority (FSRA).

During this webinar the EC has run a survey to identify the most critical areas of blockchain standardisation where more cohesion is needed. The result was that “interoperability” would benefit the most.

Five years later, interoperability is still a pressing topic. According to the ICT Rolling Plan 2025, “(there is) a lack of coherent harmonisation and interoperability that constitute obstacles to cross-border and cross-sector transactions. ... (A) safe and future-proof technological and regulatory environment, ensuring appropriate interoperability, transparency, accessibility, monitoring and governance (is needed)”. The document adds the information that the topic is currently considered by various SDOs. An important example is **WG 7 Interoperability of ISO/TC 307**.

It is also worth mentioning that INATBA has a Liaison category A with ISO/TC 307 and ITU-T and a Working Group on standardisation to support the development and adoption of interoperability guidelines, specifications and global standards.

Regarding future measures, the ICT Rolling Plan 2024 and 2025 formulated two actions:

- **Action 1:** The standardisation community should continue analysing possible standardisation gaps and identify solutions to fill them, (...). Activities may focus on governance and interoperability, (...);
- **Action 10 of 2024/2025's Action 9:** Standardisation efforts to analyze and if needed, enhance the interoperability and international compatibility of the current and pending EBSI topics and capabilities (...).

The German ICT industry association BITKOM (2023) also raised the question of internationally interoperable systems beyond eIDAS. They argue that multinational companies operate in several jurisdictions and therefore must comply with a range of different regulations. Sovereign, SSI-based documents have different security criteria than locally usable proofs and therefore require a new type of governance (see BITKOM, 2023).

There are also specific aspects on member states' level. BITKOM, for example, argues with regard to EBSI that this infrastructure should also be considered at German level when it comes to interoperable and proven standards for decentralised identities. They refer to already functional use cases with high usability in other European countries (see BITKOM, 2023).

SEEBLOCKS deliverable D3.3 (Fardad et al., 2024), issued a few months after the ICT Rolling Plan 2024 counts five publications regarding interoperability, but emphasizes that their applicability is somewhat limited: “Three publications are from the EEA” and “(mostly) applicable to

Ethereum” (p. 21). Another focus is specifically on interoperability with the Internet of Things (IoT) (see p. 21). SEEBLOCKS.EU (2025) presents an unchanged situation in this context.

On this basis, the report reveals a **“gap in a high-level, generic Interoperability standard applicable to different DLTs and use cases”** (p. 21).

In addition, it highlights that “a multidisciplinary approach to standardisation would be beneficial” because this interoperability issue “often intersects with other emerging technologies such as IoT, 5G, and AI” (p. 21).

A current standardisation project in this context is **ISO TS 23516 Blockchain and DLT Interoperability Framework**. Nevertheless, the standardisation gap still exists according to SEEBLOCKS.eu (2025).

3.4 Smart Contracts

Besides interoperability, which was identified as the most critical area of blockchain standardisation at the EU webinar “Joining Forces for Blockchain Standardisation”, other important topics identified at that event are “identity”, “Smart Contracts”, “governance” and “security”.

At ISO, **ISO/TC 307/WG 3** “Smart contracts and their applications” is of key relevance for standardisation related to Smart Contracts.

ETSI ISG PDL has published specifications on the Distributed Blockchain “Smart contracts” and “reference architecture”. It is also collaborating with TC ESI on eIDAS and supported considerations on Smart Contracts in the Data Act proposal context.

ETSI TC ESI plans to work on **policy and security requirements** for the use of ledgers as a trust service to support Smart Contracts, on the use of EUDI Wallets and advanced electronic signatures / seals for identification with Smart Contracts.

Already existing standards include according to SEEBLOCKS.eu’s deliverable D3.3 (Fardad et al., 2024):

- ETSI Group Specification (GR) PDL 004 V1.1.1 (2021-02) - Permissioned Distributed Ledgers (PDL); Smart Contracts; System Architecture and Functional Specification
- ETSI Group Report (GS) PDL 011 V2.1.1 (2022-09) - Permissioned Distributed Ledger (PDL); Specification of Requirements for Smart Contracts' architecture and security
- ISO/TR 23455:2019 Blockchain and distributed ledger technologies — Overview of and interactions between Smart Contracts in blockchain and distributed ledger technology systems.

In addition, **ISO/IEC JTC 1/SC 29** Coding of audio, picture, multimedia and hypermedia information has a work item on Smart contracts for media (FDIS 21000-23).

The ICT Rolling Plans of 2024 and 205 include in particular the following actions regarding Smart Contracts:

- **Action 7 of 2024/2025's Action 6:** ESOs to develop standards in line with the Data Act (...), in particular regarding essential requirements for smart-contracts. In addition, it would be recommended to explore a general framework for Governance of the European networks based on DLT to allow the flow of Smart Contracts between different networks.
- **Action 8 of 2024/2025's Action 7:** ESOs (2025: "when relevant") to develop the standards needed for the introduction of the Digital Euro (Central Bank Digital Currency, CBDC), if the European Central Bank (ECB) decides to its issuance, and for digital assets (MiCA Regulation), in particular to ensure interoperability with smart-contracts, legacy systems, etc., linked with either CBDCs or private money. (...)

3.5 Decentralised Identifiers (DIDs) in Smart Contracts and beyond

Decentralized identifiers (DIDs), a specific type of SSIs¹⁵ are a specific topic in the Smart Contracts context and need to consider and to be aligned with the work there.

According to the W3C (2022), DIDs are "a new type of identifier that enables verifiable, decentralized digital identity. A DID refers to any subject (e.g., a person, organization, thing, data model, abstract entity, etc.) as determined by the controller of the DID. In contrast to typical, federated identifiers, DIDs have been designed so that they may be decoupled from centralized registries, identity providers, and certificate authorities."

The W3C is a key player in the context of DID specifications. In 2022, the DID Core W3C Recommendation were published, see W3C (2022). Moreover, a charter for a new W3C DID Working Group was developed, covering a 2-year timeframe from April 2024 to April 2026, see W3C (2023).

On 9th July 2024 the Decentralized Identify Foundation, published the strategy paper "The Security and Privacy benefits of Including Decentralized Identifiers (DIDs) in the European Digital Identity Wallet Architecture and References framework." This document was collaboratively developed by various stakeholders and backed by the Decentralized Identity Foundation, Digital Credentials Consortium, and Trust Over IP Foundation.

¹⁵ See Pohlmann (2024): To enable interoperability between different SSI solutions, SSI uses the W3C specifications Decentralised Identifier (DID) as unique identifiers for all types of entities and the Verifiable Credential (VC) Data Model as a cryptographically secure data format for credentials or digital identity data and proofs.

It recommends incorporating W3C's Decentralized Identifiers (DIDs) into the European Digital Identity Wallet Architecture and Reference Framework (EUDIW ARF) to further enhance key IT-specific goals of the EU and enable a more robust, resilient, and interoperable ecosystem.

Regarding these goals, they highlight that privacy, security, and individual empowerment are fundamental considerations for a digital identity system. They recommend addressing the needs for user-centricity, privacy, security, and cross-border interoperability and commitment to a wallet architecture based on privacy-by-design.¹⁶

Also in July 2024, several organisations have announced that some DID methods are to be standardised (in addition to DIDs themselves, which are already a W3C standard (see DIF, 2024).

An important European player in the field of identifiers is CEN-CENELEC/JTC19' WG 1 "Decentralised identity management" whose scope is: "Processes, roles and practices for decentralised identity management and its support functions provided by DLTs. This includes management of identifiers, keys, evidential registries and trust anchors" (see CEN-CLC, 2022).

3.6 CO₂ footprint of blockchain

A key foundation for standardisation activities regarding the CO₂ footprint of blockchain is **Regulation (EU) 2023/1114** on markets in crypto-assets (MiCA) (European Parliament and the Council, 2023a). It highlights that:

"(t)he consensus mechanisms used for the validation of transactions in crypto-assets might have principal adverse impacts on the climate and other environment-related adverse impacts. Such consensus mechanisms should (...) deploy more environmentally friendly solutions and ensure that any principal adverse impact that they might have on the climate, and any other environment-related adverse impact, are adequately identified and disclosed by issuers of crypto-assets and crypto-asset service providers."

Important players in related standardisation areas are:

- CEN-CENELEC Working Group (WG) **JTC19** on Blockchain and Distributed Ledger Technologies, **WG2** Environmental Sustainability of Blockchain and Distributed Ledger Technologies;
- Ad hoc group (AhG) 3 FinTech in Carbon Markets under ISO/TC 322;
- ISO/TC 307/AHG 4 DLT and carbon markets.

¹⁶ <https://github.com/eu-digital-identity-wallet/eudi-doc-architecture-and-reference-framework/issues/278>. Although the document has since been removed from the website, the comments on the internet show the interest and complexity of that topic.

CEN/CENELEC/JTC19 WG 2 aims to develop a set of European standards for the environmental (climate) sustainability of Blockchain and DLTs. Currently, a Technical Report (TR) on "Environmental and Sustainability classification methodology of consensus mechanisms" is under development there.

The ICT Rolling Plan includes the following action, which was significantly modified in 2025:

Action 9 of 2024: (...) "ESO (shall) develop standards towards assessing CO₂ footprint of different blockchains/DLTs, MiCA, EU Sustainable Finance taxonomy."

Modified Action of 2025 (Action 8): "SDOs to develop standards and technical guidance, methods and tools for environmental and innovation management of DLTs to support the industry competitiveness and sustainable growth and ensure sustainability and safety for consumers. In particular in the context of the standardisation described in Action 7, SDOs to develop standards towards assessing environmental and sustainability impact including, in particular, CO₂ footprint and energy consumption of different blockchains/DLTs, MiCA, EU Sustainable Finance taxonomy."

SEEBLOCKS response to the current gaps includes, for example the funding of the following dedicated research projects:

1. A research project linked with CEN-CENELEC JTC19 WG2 facilitating the draft of a TR on the environmental sustainability classification methodology of the Blockchain and DLTs consensus mechanisms. The project included key preparatory measures to launch the ballot for approval of the specification on a complementary classification of Blockchain and DLT which shall facilitate the labelling of these technologies and cryptocurrencies according to energy efficiency categories.
2. A project of a researcher engaged in AHG3 FinTech in Carbon Markets under ISO/TC 322 (Sustainable Finance) with the following three goals:
 - Standardisation in Carbon calculation (effectiveness and accountability): Revision of ISO 14016:2020 (Environmental Management Guidelines on the assurance of environmental reports);
 - Standardisation in Carbon Market Methodologies: Partake in the standardisation work of ISO/TS 23516 (Blockchain and Distributed Ledger Technology Interoperability Framework) and ISO 14068 (Greenhouse gas management and climate change management and related activities. Carbon neutrality);
 - Standardisation in quality assurance of ETS (Development of Technical Reports).

3. A research project aimed to draft a new sustainability section for the ISO/TC 307 Strategic Business Plan and hence develop new standards with a sustainability focus.

An overview on all research projects funded by SEEBLOCKS.eu, also in the second project year is provided by SEEBLOCKS.eu (2025).

3.7 Roadmap topics based on the preliminary analysis

Table 3 summarises the key players that work on the eight roadmap topics of SEEBLOCKS.eu. There are areas in which various SDOs are active and others with more specific responsibilities. Regarding the European topics “Artificial Intelligence Act”, “Data act”, “General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR)”, “Regulation on electronic identification and trust services (EUDI – eIDAS2)” European SDOs are particularly active. The global nature of blockchain/DLT makes additional international interactions and activities particularly important.

Topic	Key current players
Specific topics related to EU regulations	
AI Act	CEN-CENELEC Focus Group Road Map on AI, CEN-CENELEC JTC 21, ETSI
Data Act	ETSI ISG DPL, Rolling Plan: various ESOs
GDPR	According to the ICT Rolling Plan ¹ : CEN & CENELEC and ETSI, and also ISO and ITU
Regulation electronic identif. & trust services	CEN & CENELEC
Topics of international relevance	
CO₂ footprint of blockchain	According to the ICT Rolling plan various ESOs Examples: CEN/CENELEC/JTC19 WG 2, ISO/TC 307/AHG 4 DLT & carbon markets, ISO/TC 322 AHG 3 FinTech in Carbon Markets
Interoperability across territories	Various SDOs and initiatives according to the ICT Rolling Plan ¹ , in particular: ISO/TC 307/WG 7, IEEE, ITU-T SG 11, ETSI ISG PDL, EEA Community project, INATBA
Smart Contracts	ETSI ISG PDL & TC ESI, ISO/TC 307/WG 3
DIDs in Smart Contracts and beyond	CEN/CENELEC/JTC19 WG 1, ISO/TC 307/WG 3, W3C
¹ The 2023 and 2024 versions were used for this preliminary analysis	

Table 3: Key SDOs for the roadmap topics

Preliminary recommendations:

Reflecting the current state of the blockchain standardisation landscape described in sections 3.1 to 3.6, we derived twelve preliminary recommendations plus an optional suggestion shown in Table 4 and described afterwards. Based on SEEBLOCKS.eu's public consultation, results of specific events strategically used by SEEBLOCKS.eu to interact with blockchain stakeholders and additional analyses, the recommendations were further developed. On this basis, chapters 4 and 5 will present specified needs for standardisation and policy making, related with concrete action items.

The first **general recommendation (R1)** calls for more SDO cooperation & liaisons in general. It relies on the many overlaps of their activities that show much potential for synergies. Likewise, the table highlights the need for our second recommendation **(R2)**, to deepen and extend the collaboration with consortia and fora, also in the context of our third recommendation below.

SEEBLOCKS.eu's third recommendation **(R3)** refers of the initiation of thematic "Joining Forces for Blockchain Standardisation" working groups and discussions on Smart Contracts, Digital Identity, Governance, Interoperability & CBDC/Crypto Assets. The foundation for this was the "Joining Forces for Blockchain Standardisation 2021" workshop, hosted by the European Commission and INATBA, which brought together standards organisations such as ISO, IEC, ITU-T, CEN CENELEC, ETSI, IEEE as well as regional bodies and national authorities from various Asian, North and South American countries, see section 3.3. According to European Commission and INATBA (2022), the workshop set a starting point for further thematic discussions related to Smart Contracts, Digital Identity, Governance, Interoperability and CBDC/Crypto Assets.

The preliminary version of this roadmap included the additional recommendation to also involve the United States in these activities. Based on new framework conditions regarding the interrelation between the EU and the U.S. which make such efforts more difficult, the current recommendation is to analyse potential new collaboration measures between both regions to strengthen the international blockchain ecosystem. The SEEBLOCKS.eu workshop at the SES conference in the United States in March 2025¹⁷ already helped to identify and reaffirm various common interests with stakeholders focussing on cooperation with Europe to build on in the future. Likewise, the need for education on blockchain standardisation was highlighted in that conference.

As Figure 7 will show, most participants of the public consultation are aware of interoperability problems between the EU, the U.S. and Asia that could be addressed by standardisation. The modifications in US-EU relations require appropriate new measures in this context.

¹⁷ See <https://seeblocks.eu/events/seeblockseu-ses-conference-2025-blockchain-transformative-power-transatlantic-digital>, <https://zenodo.org/records/15099940>,

Topic areas	Action items (recommendations/R)	Who
General	R1: Extend and deepen SDO's cooperation & liaisons due to the many overlaps R2: Extend and deepen collaborations with consortia & fora R3: Start thematic "Joining Forces for BC Standardisation" working groups/discussions on Smart Contracts, Digital Identity, Governance, Interoperability & CBDC/Crypto Assets and explore options for helpful international collaborations in this context R4: Entrust an organization such as INATBA with the roadmap's implementation	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • SDOs • DG CONNECT • (DG CONNECT +) the selected organization to implement "Joining Forces" WGs
Specific topics related to European regulations		
AI Act	R5: Further analyse the need for standardisation R6: Collaborate with AI-related TCs	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • CEN/CENELEC/JTC19, ETSI
Data Act	R7: Develop standards in line with the Data Act, especially regarding essential requirements for Smart Contracts (according to BC/DLT Action 7 of the ICT Rolling Plan 2024 (2025 Action 6))	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • CEN/CENELEC/JTC19, ETSI
GDPR	R8: Implement a forum with European NSBs and additional experts on how the GDPR can be supported in international blockchain standardisation R9: Analyse options for an EU/international standard based on DIN SPEC 4997:2020 (already addressed by the time of this roadmap's completion)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • CEN/CENELEC/JTC19 + europ. NSBs
Reg. on electr. Identification	R3.1: Start the thematic "Joining Forces for BC Standardisation" working group on Digital Identity	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • (DG CONNECT +) the selected org. • SDOs, additional experts
Topics of international relevance		
CO₂ footprint of blockchain	R10: Further work on addressing the ICT Rolling Plan's 2024 BC/DLT "Action 9: (...) develop standards towards assessing CO ₂ footprint of different BCs/DLTs, MiCA, EU Sustainable Finance taxonomy." (2025 Action 8)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • CEN (due to Europ. topics), with ISO due to ongoing int.'l standardisation
Interoperability across territories	R3.2: Start thematic "Joining Forces for BC Standardisation" discussions on Interoperability R11: Support for the development of business models for EBSI providers	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • (EU +) the selected org., SDOs, additional experts
Smart Contracts	R3.3: Start thematic "Joining Forces for BC Standardisation" discussions on Smart Contracts	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • (DG CONNECT +) the selected org., SDOs, additional experts
DIDs in Smart Contracts and beyond	R3.1 above R12: Collaborate & liaise with W3C regarding DIDs R _{opt.} (optional): If the EUDIW ARF will be further developed within the framework of standardisation, initiate discussions on the inclusion of DIDs in the relevant document	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • (DG CONNECT +) the selected org., SDOs, additional experts • CEN, ISO TC/307 • W3C, ISO/TC 307, WG4

Table 4: Roadmap topics based on the preliminary analysis

Regarding SEEBLOCKS.eu's focus areas, **R3.1** to **R3.3** refer to the implementation of "Joining Forces for Blockchain Standardisation" discussions on digital identities, Interoperability and Smart contracts. An additional recommendation (**R4**) is to entrust an organization such as INATBA with the implementation of R3 and the roadmap as a whole.

The next recommendations (**R5** and **R6**) refer to the **AI Act** and call for further analyses of the need for standardisation in this context. Collaboration with AI-related TCs is important in this context, e.g., with CEN-CENELEC JTC 21 and relevant ETSI initiatives. Recommendation **R7** refers to the **Data Act**. Adopting Action 7 of the ICT Rolling Plan 2024 (Action 6 of 2025), it entrusts ESOs with the need to develop standards in line with Regulation (EU) 2023/2854, especially regarding essential requirements for Smart Contracts.

Regarding the **GDPR**, **R8** recommends the implementation of a forum of European NSBs and additional experts on how the GDPR or its specific values and principles can be supported in international blockchain standardisation. The second recommendation related to the GDPR (**R9**) recommends analysing options for a European or even international standard based on DIN SPEC 4997:2020-04, titled in English "Privacy by Blockchain Design: A standardised model for processing personal data using blockchain technology".

Update of the roadmap's final version: Based on the DIN SPEC, a European standard on the topic is currently being developed as part of a project in CEN/CENELEC JTC19 WG3 (PII in Blockchain and DLT) under the leadership of a former SEEBLOCKS.eu beneficiary as convener and project manager. The second meeting of the experts took place in May 2025.

Addressing ecological sustainability, the CO₂ footprint of blockchain is another action item. In this context, **R10** calls for further work on addressing the ICT Rolling Plan 2024's Action 9 (2025's Action 8) to develop standards towards assessing CO₂ footprint of different BCs/DLTs, MiCA, EU Sustainable Finance taxonomy.

An additional recommendation regarding interoperability is to support the development of business models for EBSI providers by appropriate measures (**R11**). A European funding scheme is desired in this context. The last two recommendations refer to specific aspects of DIDs. **R12** recommends ESOs to collaborate and liaise with W3C in this context. Another topic is the ARF. If the ARF will be further developed within the framework of standardisation, discussions on the inclusion of DIDs in the relevant document should be initiated (**R_{opt.}**).

Specific topics for the different "Joining Forces for Blockchain Standardisation" Working Groups and discussion on Smart Contracts, Digital Identity, Governance, Interoperability & CBDC/Crypto Assets were derived by our consultation presented in the next section. It also describes the next steps regarding the Artificial Intelligence Act, Data Act, the GDPR and the CO₂ footprint of blockchain.

D4.9 Blockchain/DLT Standardisation Policy Roadmap (final)	 Supporting Europe's effort in Blockchain/DLT Standardisation
Grant Agreement No.: 101091933	

As described above, the recommendations were further developed and modified based on SEEBLOCKS.eu's public consultation and an additional review in SEEBLOCKS.eu's second project year. On this basis, chapters 4 and 5 will present action items for standardisation and regarding regulatory and other policy measures to support blockchain/DLT.

4. Roadmap elements

4.1 Building blocks based on SEEBLOCKS.eu's public consultation

4.1.1 Action items regarding data exchange, electronic identification & trust services, DIDs, Smart Contracts, data protection & AI

A **need for action regarding interoperability** was already unveiled in SEEBLOCKS.eu's first public consultation and will be considered specifically in section 4.1.3. Visualised by Figure 5, targeted additional questions of the second consultation dealt with **additional needs** for standardisation and regulatory support regarding data exchange, electronic identification and trust services, Decentralised Identifiers (DIDs) and Smart Contracts, the CO₂ footprint, data protection and AI.

Figure 5: Needs for standards and/or regulations in selected areas to support blockchain/DLT

According to most participants, **specific needs for standardisation and regulatory support** besides interoperability aspects refer to **data exchange, followed by electronic identification and DIDs**. Likewise, the participants' majority indicated that standardisation needs related to the **CO₂ footprint and data protection** exist in the blockchain/DLT context. Regarding AI, there were more "no" than "yes" answers and most participants selected the answer option "Don't know" in response to the AI-related question. Section 4.1.2 to 4.6 will provide more details on the specific needs for action.

4.1.2 Specific action items related to interoperability

Interoperability issues have particularly attracted the attention of SEEBLOCKS.eu, as participants of the first public consultation had pointed out the need for action in this area. Therefore, the second consultation included two specific questions regarding this topic. The first one asked the participants to rate the importance of three action items to support blockchain interoperability.

Figure 6: Ranking of action items related to interoperability

According to Figure 6, most participants regarded the action items “Standards for data formats and Interoperability -- (eIDAS2, SWIFT)” and “Guidelines for security, privacy and access -- (DORA,

GDPR, EU Digital Identity, eIDAS2)” as high priority, signalling an urgent need for action in this respect. A few of these topics represent also blockchain governance topics, in particular privacy, security and access rights.¹⁸

The action item "Governance models to enable interoperability across the tech stack -- (Cloud Computing, Peer to Peer computing, Edge and fog computing)" of SEEBLOCKS.eu's first public consultation, which had a very broad scope beyond the core understanding of blockchain governance¹⁹ was mainly ranked as medium priority. At the same time, various specific blockchain governance topics were classified as short-term priorities by the second round's participants, see e.g., section 4.5.2 and specific parts on the above-mentioned topics security and access rights in section 4.1.3.

The next question was focused on trans-continental interoperability and asked whether there are interoperability problems of blockchain/DLT between the EU, the U.S. and Asia that could be addressed by standardisation. If a participant answered yes, additional explanations were requested. According to Figure 7, most participants think that such problems exist.

Their answers were added by various descriptions, which are shown in Annex 2. The topics include, for example, data exchange, data portability, identity management and transatlantic wallet interoperability. The answers on the next questions, presented in Figure 8, will describe these topics in more detail.

The next part of the consultation collected participants' descriptions of **additional needs for blockchain/DLT-related standardisation and regulation to support the interoperability** of blockchain/DLT. Some of these responses also included suggestions for supporting blockchain/DLT in general.

In detail, participants formulated eleven standardisation suggestions across all blockchain topics and added additional comments according to Annex 2.

Example answers referred to needs for standards for data and identify formats, data exchange, security, interoperability between DIDs, standards “around auditing”, and “rulebooks by industry verticals”.

¹⁸ Principle 8 of ISO TS 23635 Blockchain and Distributed Ledger Technologies – Guidelines for governance is to ensure security and privacy. Sylvain Cariou from Crystalchain and AFNOR delegate, for example relates the following topics to governance: evolutions (regulation, perimeter, volumes), litigation management, KYC (know your client), access rights, incentives, balance of power, transparency and security, see, e.g., EBCC (2022)

¹⁹ See previous footnote

Figure 7: Perception of interoperability problems between the EU, the U.S. and Asia that could be addressed by standardisation

An additional contribution sent to SEEBLOCKS.eu by e-mail discussed EBSI-related needs for action in detail:

“(standardisation of different elements (...); namely, there are many public draft standards (IETF, OIDC, ...) where EBSI already completed a profile and would need further standardisation with official SDOs.”

Regarding specific **needs for regulatory support**, participants provided 15 sets of suggestions according to Annex 2. Partly, the entries included keywords only, e.g., "DeFi" (Decentralized Finance) or "EIDAS2", added by more details in following parts of the consultation, e.g., related to the Financial Action Task Force.

More specific suggestions included, e.g., “legal validity of Smart Contracts” and, as part of a comment on interoperability between DIDs: “some harmonization on the trusted registries, as each identity model defines it different”.

Additional recommendations referred to broader policy measures to support blockchain/DLT such as funding specific projects or the initiation of additional targeted regulatory sandboxes.

4.1.3 Short, medium and long-term standardisation priorities

The participants of the second consultation's survey were also asked to classify eight blockchain standardisation topic areas regarding short, medium and long-term priorities, which is illustrated by Figure 8. The priority of interoperability and data formats were already highlighted in the first consultation and its follow-up questions (see also Figure 6 and Figure 7). Therefore, the importance analysis visualized in Figure 8 only considered the priority of additional topics.

Figure 8: Stakeholders' short, medium & long-term standardisation priorities beyond the key data exchange & interoperability topics

DIDs and Smart Contracts, which SEEBLOCKS.eu often views as a combined topic, are analysed separately in the survey due to the importance of both areas.

According to Figure 8, there were three topics, for which the option "short-term" was given most often, four topics, for which the participants specified the relevant time frame as up to "medium-term" priority²⁰ and one topic, for which the suggestion "long-term" was chosen most often:

Short-term priorities besides the interoperability and data format topics of Figure 6 include the items "Electronic identification and trust services (e.g., related to EUDI - eIDAS2)", "Decentralised Identity (e.g., SSI, DID, eIDAS2)" and "Smart Contract Security".

Medium-term priorities consist of additional data exchange topics and the remaining Interoperability topics of Figure 5, but also of data protection and the CO₂ footprint, which the participants' majority consists of short OR medium-term priority.

Long-term priorities are related to "Artificial Intelligence and blockchain (e.g., governance and transparency layer on DLT)".

The additional analyses for the roadmap's final version modified the resulting implications and also consider the overarching need of standardisation education. In parallel with the dynamic environment of blockchain standardisation, which mainly requests short and medium-term standardisation activities, education in blockchain standardisation is a permanent need, covering short-, medium and long-term horizons. It is described in section 4.3.

The results were also very useful to get further insight related to the results of Figure 4. Electronic identification and trust services, DIDs and smart contracts belonging to the topics for which the participants most often indicated a need for action were also regarded as short-term priorities in Figure 7. Likewise, the last topic of the list related to AI was considered a long-term priority.

Details on all the needs listed above are described in the chapters 4.2 to 4.5 and chapter 5. In addition, it was highlighted by an additional e-mail to SEEBLOCKS.eu that EBSI would benefit from an overview of business requirements and insight how and where this infrastructure can help businesses. Besides several materials for the early adopters, a framework for business capability identification and mapping is regarded as useful.

4.2 Overview of the roadmap elements

Based on SEEBLOCKS.eu's public consultation and Figure 8 in section 4.1, additional input gained at the stakeholder events in the project's second project year and updates of the ICT Rolling Plan

²⁰ Also including topics, for which the majority indicated short OR medium-term priority

2025, the roadmap's short-, medium- and long-term standardisation activity were further specified, see Table 5. The standardisation priorities are described in the following sections while priorities for policy support will be described in chapter 5.2.

Chapter 3 described the need for Joining Forces for Blockchain Standardisation working groups to bring the various stakeholders together. In line with various blockchain standardisation experts mentioned in chapter 3, the consultation also highlighted the specific interrelations between standardisation and policy making and the need for targeted interactions in the regard. Emphasizing and extending the recommendation on establishing "Joining Forces for Blockchain Standardisation" working groups, the **first short-term priority** is therefore to establish "Joining Forces for Blockchain Standardisation and Regulation" working groups that also have a specific focus on dialogues between both domains. Another topic is a guiding standard for security, privacy and access that specifically considers the European requirements, which will be explained in detail in section 4.4.2.

Standardisation		Broader policy-based support
<p>Short-Term: starting 2025</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Joining Forces for Blockchain Standardisation and Regulation working groups Guiding standard for security, privacy and access that specifically considers the European requirements of DORA, GDPR, EU Digital Identity, eIDAS2 Interoperability and data formats Electronic identification and trust services (e.g., related to EUDI - eIDAS2) Decentralised Identity (e.g., SSI, DID, eIDAS2) Smart Contract security Sustainability and safety for consumers, standards towards assessing environmental and sustainability impact including, in particular, CO₂ footprint and energy consumption of different blockchains/DLTs, MiCA, EU Sustainable Finance taxonomy¹ Blockchain-supported trusted AI 		<p>Short-term priorities</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> Joining Forces for Blockchain Standardisation and Regulation" working groups Legal validity and enforceability of Smart Contracts DID policies and suitable regulatory framework conditions to support the interoperability between DIDs Support education on blockchain standardisation
<p>Medium-Term: starting 2027</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Additional needs regarding data formats and data exchange Additional data protection topics 	<p>Long-Term: starting 2027+</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Needs for additional² cross-technology standardisation topics in the blockchain context, also with specific consideration of ethical aspects 	<p>Medium-term priorities</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> Suitable regulatory framework conditions for blockchain governance Regulatory support for trusted registries Additional regulatory measures for Decentralised Finance Sustainability framework Specify standardisation education, analyse updated education needs
<p>Long-term priorities</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> Adjust blockchain and ICT standardisation education strategies 		

¹ Updated priority based on the ICT Rolling Plan 2025, replacing the sustainability priority of this report's first version, which is already considered by the time of this report's completion
² In addition to blockchain and AI

Note: a more detailed version of this figure is included in the executive summary of this report

Table 5: Short, medium and long-term priorities for standardisation and policies to support for blockchain/DLT

Other short-term priorities are interoperability and data formats, "Electronic identification and trust services (e.g., related to EUDI - eIDAS2)", "Decentralised Identity (e.g., SSI, DID, eIDAS2)", "Smart Contract security", sustainability and Artificial Intelligence and blockchain.

Medium-term priorities consist of additional data exchange topics and the remaining Interoperability topics of Figure 5, but also of data protection.

Long-term priorities refer to further cross-technology topics and a refinement of education strategies.

4.3 Standardisation education as overarching priority

Besides the suggestions for specific standardisation measures, a participant in the public consultation gave the recommendation to “Increase public awareness and education initiatives to inform stakeholders about the potential benefits and applications of blockchain technology”. After the publication of the preliminary version of this report, the importance of education in blockchain standardisation became even more evident, particularly in SEEBLOCKS.eu’s events and communications with stakeholders at the beginning of 2025. To effectively address the challenges and opportunities in this field, a structured educational approach is essential, spanning short-, medium-, and long-term strategies.

Short-Term (Starting 2025): A key roadmap goal is to increase the number of education measures on blockchain standardisation. SEEBLOCKS.eu members help to address this goal by offering several webinars after the project’s duration. Additional measures have to be specified. CEN-CENELEC’s new “STAIR” working group²¹ is particularly encouraged to specify a schedule with specific measures.

An important foundation of education on standardisation is the International Workshop Agreement (IWA) 30-1 on the Competence of Standards Professionals, Part 1: In Companies (ISO, 2019). This initiative is designed to prepare professionals in companies for the complexities of standardisation, equipping them with the necessary skills and knowledge.

Medium-Term (Starting 2027): From 2027 onward, the focus will shift to specified education that considers the final results of the then finished EDU4Standards.eu project (<https://edu4standards.eu/>). This phase will involve comprehensive analyses of updated education needs to ensure that training programs are aligned with current industry demands and provide practical, applicable skills for participants.

Long-Term (Starting 2027+): In the long term, strategies for blockchain and ICT standardisation education need to be refined by initiatives such as StandICT.eu 2029 to meet stakeholders’ evolving requirements. StandICT.eu 2029 will be the successor to StandICT.eu 2026

²¹ The SEEBLOCKS.eu consortium assumes that this group will present itself to the public with its new, official name in summer 2025.

(<https://standict.eu/>) and therefore have a longer time horizon. As StandICT.eu 2026, the project aims to support ICT standardisation in Europe. Public information about this project will be available soon. This ongoing adjustment will ensure that educational offerings remain relevant and prepare professionals for future developments and trends in standardisation. The involvement of StandICT in this roadmap also considers the involvement of StandICT in fundamental earlier activities described in this roadmap, in particular in the first “Joining Forces for Blockchain Standardisation” event (European Commission and INATBA, 2022).

By implementing this multi-faceted educational strategy, the education on blockchain standardisation will serve overarching needs in blockchain standardisation, addressing immediate needs while laying a solid foundation for future educational requirements.

Standardisation education is a standardisation and policy topic simultaneously. It is already mentioned here but specified in the policy section.

4.4 Short-term priorities

4.4.1 Creation of “Joining Forces for Blockchain Standardisation and Regulation” working groups as fundamental action item

As described in chapter 2, the key foundations of SEEBLOCKS.eu’s roadmap development were its analysis of the current state of blockchain/DLT-related standardisation and policy making and its public consultation. Besides various hints and suggestions of the first round, a specific roadmapping survey was used in the second round. It strategically discussed the topics described in chapter 3 and those of the first round for further specifications.

Chapter 3 described the need for “Joining Forces for Blockchain Standardisation” working groups to bring the various stakeholders together. The consultation even showed the attractiveness of broadening the scope of these groups by highlighting the particular interactions between blockchain standardisation and the work of policy makers. For example, the consultation indicated the following links between the need for blockchain standardisation and regulation (see Annex 2):

“Need to have consistent measurements [by standardisation] to begin with - what is measured and how. Then regulation.” (a participant’s comment regarding the CO₂ footprint of blockchain)

“Implementing acts need to refer to standards” (a participant’s comment regarding eIDAS and blockchain standardisation)

Likewise, various blockchain standardisation experts emphasized the need for action in the regard, for example at a webinar on blockchain standardisation organized by the European Blockchain Center: “dialogue between both groups (standards and regulation) is very important” (Roman Beck,²² head of the Danish ISO/TC 307 standardisation group), “the complementary nature between standards and regulation (has to be considered)” (Gayan Benedict,²³ Australian representative of ISO/TC 307).²⁴ More specifically, Mr. Beck formulated regarding a current standard of the TC:

“There is always this kind of chicken-and-egg problem. We hear, we have to wait with standards until the regulators formulated the framework and when you talk to the regulators they say, we still lack the terminology, we lack the standards that emerge that need to be regulated and therefore... I think it is very important that this process of developing frameworks – regulatory frameworks as well as standards frameworks, that they correspond.”

Table 6 in chapter 4.8 will propose four specific working groups to connect standardisation and regulation experts related to this roadmap’s topics.

Another dimension of these working groups mentioned in chapter 3 refers to international collaborations. In this context, SEEBLOCKS.eu’s workshop “Blockchain Nexus: Bridging Innovations and Standards for Tomorrow’s Digital Frontier” in Japan in June 2024²⁵ and the contributions from Asia and South America to SEEBLOCK.eu’s impact event in April 2025²⁶, in particular to its panel discussion on “international (standardisation) priorities within blockchain, DLT & complementary landscape” provided helpful insights. They demonstrated not only the blockchain-related expertise of both regions, but also the need for further deepening cooperation with them, also to address the cross-continental interoperability challenges emphasized in SEEBLOCKS.eu’s public consultation.

As an example, a legal expert from South America who participated in SEEBLOCKS.eu’s panel discussions at its impact event, noted about his region that

“... we need to acknowledge that it’s a different region. How we regulate, how we import other standardization models, is according to the vision of North America, but with Latin American elements. We have a trans-national SDO, but we have seen that businesses and groups comply by making it a law, by creating rules. This is a very Latin

²² European Blockchain Center/IT-University of Copenhagen – Denmark

²³ Salesforce – Australia

²⁴ See <https://www.ebcc.eu/online-webinar-iso-blockchain-governance-standard/>

²⁵ See <https://seeblocks.eu/news/blockchain-land-rising-sun-seeblocks-ieee-compsac-2024-osaka-japan>

²⁶ See <https://seeblocks.eu/events/seeblockseu-final-event-how-dep-project-seeblockseu-has-impacted-european-blockchaindl>

American cultural phenomenon, to have rules to comply to. There has been a lot of legal research on why this is the case, but the fact is that there is this mindset about making standards directly into laws in the countries."

This is in contrast to many other countries where standards have an interplay with regulations but tend to be kept separate; in fact, in some countries there is a place for the concept of standards with only voluntary compliance. For this reason, global collaboration to understand the cultural backgrounds and harmonize regulatory approaches is vital.

The good practice of the first "Joining Forces for Blockchain Standardisation" event held with participants from Japan, Brazil and many other countries is therefore to be continued, and trans-continental relations further strengthened.

4.4.2 Interoperability and data formats

According to Figure 6, an overwhelming majority of the participants is aware of international blockchain-related interoperability problems that could be addressed by standardisation.

As mentioned at the beginning of this chapter, the need for interoperability standards was specifically highlighted in SEEBLOCKS.eu's first public consultation. Dedicated questions of the second round showed the high priority of:

- "Standards for data formats and Interoperability -- (eIDAS2, SWIFT)" and
- "Guidelines for security, privacy and access -- (DORA, GDPR, EU Digital Identity, eIDAS2)",

added by the specific topics such as data exchange, data portability, and transatlantic wallet interoperability.

The first specific suggestion for standardisation in this regard were already given in response to the open question on relevant blockchain-related standardisation topics at the beginning of the second consultation. Specifically, the following needs for specification were formulated there:

- Which is the semantic data catalogue to exchange attributes?
- How do you model attributes like financial data for legal persons, organizational structure, power of attorney, education data?
- How to make a credential that is machine readable?

Participants also highlighted the need for SSI and DID interoperability as described in section 4.1. In summary, the following action items were derived:

- Initiate the development of interoperability standards for SSI and DIDs in collaboration with key stakeholders from these areas as described in previous sections (see also the separate section on decentralized identity).
- Further analyse and address the needs for additional standards for data formats, data exchange and data portability according to current needs.

A first solution to provide guidelines for security, privacy and access is provided by ISO/TS 23635:2022 Blockchain and distributed ledger technologies — Guidelines for governance. According to ISO, this document provides “guiding principles and a framework for the governance of DLT systems.” It “also provides guidance on the fulfilment of governance, including risk and regulatory contexts, that supports the effective, efficient, and acceptable use of DLT systems.”

DORA, GDPR, EU Digital Identity and eIDAS2 established specific requirements in this context. On this basis, additional standardisation activities on the European level are needed to also consider these European needs. An additional need for action is therefore:

- Develop a guiding standard for security, privacy and access that specifically considers the European requirements of DORA, GDPR, EU Digital Identity, eIDAS2.

The development of this standard shall specifically address the fragmentation of the blockchain standardisation landscape and specifically involve the “Joining Forces for Blockchain Standardisation and Regulation” working groups.

Various standardisation activities towards interoperability and security took place in parallel with the creation of the preliminary and final version of this report and SEEBLOCKS.eu’s report D3.3 as one of their key foundations. Examples include the creation of IEEE 3205-2023 - Blockchain Interoperability Protocol, EEA DLT Interoperability Specification 1.0 (2024) and ISO/TS 23526:2023 - Security aspects for digital currencies. Nevertheless, the EU’s ICT Rolling Plan emphasizes permanent interoperability problems that need further standardisation activities, see also section 4.5.2 for further details.

Regarding the GDPR, the initiation of a new standardisation project at CEN/CENELEC JTC19 WG3 (PII in Blockchain and DLT) was an important step.

An important already existing document regarding ethical aspects is also Beck & Agerskov (2024): “Ethical Guidelines for Blockchain Systems”, which addresses European values specifically. According to the European Commission²⁷, „the guidelines comprehensively address the following thematic areas: Fairness, Privacy, Security, Economic Accountability and Societal Responsibility“.

²⁷ See https://blockchain-observatory.ec.europa.eu/news/ethical-guidelines-blockchain-systems-2024-05-15_en

As shown in Figure 7, most participants of the public consultation are also aware of interoperability problems between the EU, the U.S. and Asia that could be addressed by standardisation. The modifications in US-EU relations require appropriate new measures in this context.

4.4.3 Electronic identification and trust services

As shown in Figure 8, most participants of the public consultation also regarded electronic identification and trust services as a short-term standardisation priority.

An open question on blockchain/DLT standardisation needs at the beginning of the survey has already led to three proposals in this respect. They refer to key management, identity management and the EU Digital Identity Wallet (EUDIW), see Annex 2, section “General suggestions regarding the short-, medium, and long-term priorities”.

The second part of the survey contained a specific question on needs for standardisation in this area, which further emphasized the importance of the topics mentioned above (see Annex 2 - Recommendations related to identification and trusted services). Selected action items derived from the answers include:

- A European standard framework for blockchain / DLT solutions for EU Digital Identity Wallet (EUDIW);
- EU-wide identity and wallet management for healthcare, financial and further transactions across Europe and worldwide;
- Signature standards on blockchains and standards for oracles;
- Qualified Electronic Ledger Certification process and guidelines;
- Decentralized Public Key Infrastructure (DPKI).²⁸

On this basis, we defined the following specific standardisation topics:

²⁸ An interesting observation was that the topic was highlighted in various sections of the survey:

- Related to identification and trusted services they highlighted: “(the need) to ensure provenance and trust for dPKI model” and that “(identification and trusted services are) one of the major objectives for Decentralized PKI (DPKI) standardization activity”
- Regarding data exchange, they described that “public-key infrastructure is the basis for secure data exchange. A PKI based on blockchain as DPKI will provide global support.”
- With regards to the GDPR they described that “the DPKI project includes capabilities for identity management and access control, which is important for GDPR.”
- In addition, they described that “it could be interesting to explore how DPKI could support DIDs”

- Initiate a CEN-CLC-ETSI JWG on EBSI-related standardisation;
- Analyse suitable topics for further standardisation measures to support EBSI and initiate appropriate follow-up measures;
- Analyse the needs for sector-specific standards related to EBSI specifically;
- Further analyse standardisation needs related to DPKI and implement appropriate follow-up measures;
- Initiate the creation of a European standard framework for blockchain / DLT solution for EU Digital Identity Wallet (EUDIW);
- Work on the creation of signature standards on blockchains;
- Further check the needs for qualified Electronic Ledger certification processes and guidelines.

Standards for oracles are considered in section 4.4.5.

4.4.4 Decentralised Identity

Another topic selected by the participants as short-term priority was “decentralized identity.” To guide the consultation’s participants, SSI, DID and eIDAS2 were included as example topics belonging to this topic area.

One of the suggestions in response to the request for blockchain standardisation topics in general referred to DIDs as follows: “bridging Decentralised Identifier / Identity and Blockchain / DLT” while considering differences between the international and European perspective as the European market also requires including eIDAS2.

“A worldwide standard bridging Decentralised Identifier / Identity and Blockchain / DLT beyond W3C DID and VC (...) and a European standard covering the European specificities including eIDAS2 regulation.”

The term “bridging” is an example for various descriptions that the participants used synonymously for “interoperability” and compatibility solutions.

The first part of the consultation on needs for action in general also showed additional standardisation needs related to SSI and DIDs:

- “How a credential managed by EUDIW could be recognized by another SSI system that works in another region? (“transatlantic” wallet interoperability). Recognized means: ascertain its validity in the origin SSI and make it legally binding in the other”;

- “Interoperability between DIDs is the key, and maybe some harmonization on the trusted registries, as each identity model defines it different”;
- “Interoperability between blockchains at protocol level will be practically impossible, but easier at DID level. (...) some standardization work here must be done to add interoperability features.”

The specific consultation section on decentralised identity contained twelve suggestions, for example related to formats and interoperability in general and a note repeating the need for the above-mentioned bridging standard (see Annex 2 – section Recommendations related to Decentralised Identifiers (DIDs).

The responses also included, for example, the comment “correlation to accounts, vaults and other high-level structures through *correct use* of identities”, showing that more guidance regarding the use of identities would be helpful.

In summary, the following action items were derived from the consultation:

- Further work on DID interoperability; initiate standardisation bridging DIDs and Blockchain / DLT beyond W3C DID and VC (...) by also considering the European specificities including the eIDAS2 regulation;
- Further work on support by standardisation that a credential managed by EUDIW can be recognized by other SSI systems from other regions ("transatlantic" wallet interoperability).

Update based on an additional stakeholder action for the completion of this final version of the roadmap:

1. There is now a new work item for DIDs in the European standardization group CEN/CLC/JTC 19/WG 01, which is called: "N210 - Functional and interoperability requirements on Decentralized Identifier (DID)". This is intended to take into account precisely European requirements with DIDs and in particular in relation to eIDAS2. The document is still at a rather early stage, but there are initial contributions from experts and regular meetings.

2. There is a draft charter for a possible new W3C working group for the standardisation of "important" DID methods. The specific framework condition is that there is currently a standard for the DID core technology, but no standards for DID methods: <https://w3c.github.io/did-methods-wg-charter/2025/did-methods-wg.html>

3. In parallel, there is also a working group in DIF that deals with selection criteria for "recommended" DID methods: <https://github.com/decentralized-identity/did-methods/>

4. There is a possible overlap with the EU Cyber Resilience Act (CRA), which deals with security issues of the EUDI wallet, among other things. According to stakeholder opinion, it could be useful to also work on security aspects of DIDs within the framework of CRA, e.g. in the CEN TC 224 standardization group.

5. There is a further possible overlap with the EU Digital Product Passport (DPP) initiatives. Here, work is also being done on the use of DIDs for DPPs, e.g. in the CEN/CLC/JTC 24/WG 02 standardization group.

These new developments require specific consideration and emphasize the importance of section 3's recommendations R1: Extend and deepen SDO's cooperation & liaisons due to the many overlaps - R3.1: Start the thematic "Joining Forces for BC Standardisation" working group on Digital Identity, R2: Extend and deepen collaborations with consortia & for a and R12: Collaborate & liaise with W3C regarding DIDs.

4.4.5 Smart Contract security

Various action items related to Smart Contracts were described in section 3. Specific standardisation needs related to Smart Contract security are regarded as the fifth short-term priority area of blockchain/DTL standardisation. In this context, the participants of the consultation formulated, in particular, two specific suggestions: "Standards for audits and security metrics" and "standardisation for blockchain Oracle programs", referring to "entities that connect blockchains to external systems, thereby enabling Smart Contracts to execute based upon inputs and outputs from the real world" (Chainlink, 2024). Further steps are described in section 5.

Referencing various other sources, SEEBLOCKS.eu (2025) emphasised the existing need for standardisation measures in the context of smart contracts.

4.4.6 Environmental sustainability and CO₂ footprint

Standardisation related to the CO₂ footprint of blockchain belonged to the standardisation topics for which specific suggestions were given most frequently in the beginning of the public consultation already. The most detailed recommendation was:

"A worldwide standard for designing sustainable Blockchain / DLT systems and for assessing and monitoring the environmental footprint (electric consumption, carbon footprint / CO₂ emission, water footprint, electronic waste, (...)) of Blockchain / DLT

systems (ongoing works at ISO/TC307/WG3, WG6 and WG8) and a European standard covering the European specificities (ongoing work at CEN-CENELEC/JTC19/WG2)”

The request for detailed suggestions related to the CO₂ footprint of blockchain led, for example to the following comments:

- “Electronic ledgers in eIDAS2 have to be eco-sustainable and there are no standards to define what this means”;
- “Standards to calculate CO₂ footprint of each transaction”;
- “Need to have consistent measurements to begin with - what is measured and how.”;
- “Environmental footprint to be addressed more broadly: electric consumption, carbon footprint / CO₂ emission, water footprint, electronic waste, (...)”

Section 3 described the work on an ISO TR on the environmental sustainability classification methodology of blockchain and DLTs consensus mechanisms; the revision of ISO 14016:2020 and Carbon calculation; the work on ISO/TS 23516 “TS 23516 “Blockchain and Distributed Ledger Technology — Interoperability Framework” and ISO 14068 “Greenhouse gas management and climate change management and related activities. Carbon neutrality” and a project aimed to draft a new sustainability section for the ISO/TC 307 Strategic Business Plan.

On this basis, the following action items were derived for the first version of this roadmap for further considerations related to the future steps specified by that section:

- Develop a definition what eco-sustainability means in the blockchain context;
- Develop standards to calculate the CO₂ footprint per transaction (if not yet addressed by the time of this roadmap’s implementation);
- Based on the need for a definition described above, check which additional sustainability aspects need further standardisation.

Various recommendations also referred to regulation. The following comments stand for various similar suggestions in this regard:

- “(Based on standardized values) regulation of what CO₂ footprint is acceptable and how to force internalization of cost”²⁹;
- “Some regulation on max CO₂ footprint per block registered on the ledger. As the cost is incremental, sharding and other techniques should be enforced”.

²⁹ Regarding acceptable footprints, another participant wrote, for example: “Certain BC architectures (proof of work), (...), are extremely compute-intensive. This needs to be restricted (...), both for acceptability of DLT and for planetary reasons.”

As shown above, the item on the CO₂ footprint was presented with a time restriction. This means that several activities addressing the relevant priority of the roadmap's first version were already visible. In parallel, we noticed updated recommendations in the ICT Rolling Plan in this context. For this reason, we decided to adopt the relevant recommendation of the Rolling Plan:

“Develop standards and technical guidance for environmental and innovation management of DLTs to support the industry competitiveness and sustainable growth and ensure sustainability and safety for consumers, develop standards towards assessing environmental and sustainability impact including, in particular, CO₂ footprint and energy consumption of different blockchains/DLTs, MiCA, EU Sustainable Finance taxonomy.”

In line with the presentation of the topic in the ICT Rolling Plan, this roadmap classifies this topic as a short-term priority.

The following recommendation of the roadmaps first version

“Based on the need for a definition described above, check which additional sustainability aspects need further standardisation”

was also integrated into this priority topic.

4.4.7 Artificial Intelligence and blockchain

Artificial Intelligence is an important standardisation topic with engaged European and international standardisation activities. A key strategic document in this context was the CEN-CENELEC Focus Group Road Map on Artificial Intelligence (CEN-CLC, 2020).³⁰ It mentions blockchain as an AI use case, showing that a link between both standardisation areas exists. However, more specifications are not given. Another important strategic document is the German Standardization Roadmap on Artificial Intelligence (DIN, DKE, 2022). Needs for joint AI- and blockchain standardisation do not belong to the key priorities of this document. It mentions, however a research project called IMPULSE, which developed “a holistic AI and blockchain technology supporting, GDPR-compliant eID, and actionable roadmaps and recommendations for the adoption, scale-up and sustainability of such advanced eID technologies by public services and for policymakers.” As described in section 4.3, the eID is also an important part of this roadmap.

Regarding blockchain and AI, participants of SEEBLOCKS.eu's consultation only gave a few suggestions regarding AI-related blockchain standardisation, which summarized in the AI section of

³⁰ See also the work of CEN-CENELEC Joint Technical Committee 21 'Artificial Intelligence' and the [CEN-CENELEC response to the EC White Paper on AI](#)

Annex 2. An important comment referred to potential standards for blockchain(-based) assurance mechanisms to address and ideally avoid AI-generated fake information, pictures, etc.

As written in section 3, the **ICT Rolling Plans 2024 and 2025** (European Commission, 2024b and 2025) include six AI-related actions in a specific AI chapter without specific references to blockchain/DLT. Stakeholder's input for the first version of this roadmap classified standardisation needs related to blockchain and AI as a long-term priority.

SEEBLOCKS.eu's impact event in April 2025 modified this picture. Panel 1 on "Blockchain, DLT & other ICT needs within Europe" and Panel 2, titled "From local needs to global standards: International Priorities within Blockchain, DLT & complementary landscape" highlighted the need for cross-technology standardisation as a short-term priority, particularly related to blockchain and AI, and immediate needs related to DLT & Trust, using blockchain for data provenance in AI. Further analyses of this topic drew SEEBLOCKS.eu's attention to pioneering work of the German Blockchain Bundesverband (Bundesblock) in this context, see Figure 9.

Among other things, a Bundesblock position statement summarized in the figure suggests a round table to develop standards for trusted / blockchain-based AI in Germany.

This roadmap extends this scope and suggests establishing such interactions on a European or even international level and link it with the Joining Forces for Blockchain Standardisation activities.

'Trusted AI' - a model for Europe

How the combination of blockchain and AI can create more trust in future artificial intelligence applications

An appeal to politics, business and society / Berlin, 15 January 2025

Even more than two years after the introduction of the first mass market applications, many fundamental issues in the broad field of artificial intelligence (AI) still need to be clarified. Immense social problems such as fake news, election manipulation, many forms of online fraud or cyberbullying. For exponential, i.e. even more powerful technologies such as AI, society, politics and science should think very carefully, especially in view of the rapid technological development - and force strategic discussions on the emerging challenges of the interaction between AI, blockchain and web3.

Unfortunately, the current legal framework, in particular the EU's AI Act adopted in 2024, does not yet provide sufficient answers to these challenges, which will arise from the merging of AI, blockchain and, in future, quantum computing. Blockchain technology is the technology that can be used to establish and maintain governance structures and any kind of rule-based control in this "backend of the future" and thus ensure trust.

In this context, the Bundesblock is calling for the establishment of an innovation roundtable for Germany and the initiation of an interdisciplinary forum with representatives from politics, business and science in order to develop concrete measures and standards.

Source: Blockchain Bundesverband (2025), translated

Figure 9: Additional voices related to SEEBLOCKS' impact event's topic Trusted AI: excerpts of a Bundesblock position paper

Positioning the topic as a short-term priority also considers that group of SEEBLOCKS.eu's open consultation participants, who, in contrast to the majority, have already classified blockchain and AI as a short-term priority. An example for this view is reflected by the following quotation, taken from Annex 2 of this report: "It might be necessary in the near future when AI solutions become widely applied in the industry. For blockchain-AI solutions standardization will also become necessary. Certain AI-generated or AI-modified data might be stored in blockchain, etc."

4.5 Medium-term priorities

4.5.1 Additional data exchange topics

In addition to the high-priority standardisation issues related to data formats and data exchange described in chapter 4.3, e.g., related to DID, participants also indicated the need for medium-term data exchange standardisation, but the suggestions were very general. In parallel, the list of action items, perceived as short-term priority was quite long, which means that some of its topics can probably only be dealt with in the medium term.

4.5.2 Governance policies to support interoperability

According to Figure 5, governance-related models to support interoperability in general are also regarded as medium-term priority while participants indicated a short-term priority of guidelines with a specific focus on EU regulations in addition to the already existing standard ISO/TS 23635:2022 Blockchain and distributed ledger technologies — Guidelines for governance developed by ISO/TC 307/WG 5 Governance.

The participants also emphasized the importance of regulatory support in this respect. It was highlighted that interoperability problems of blockchain/DLT between the EU, the U.S. and Asia could be addressed “mainly at the governance level ((by) legal recognition of blockchain-based solutions).”

Specifically, participants described the importance of implementing “coherent global regulations and establish(ing) uniform standards that address data security, privacy, and governance.” All the three standardisation topics were also mentioned several additional times in the consultation and section 4.4.2 already addressed this need for standardisation. The need for an appropriate interplay between blockchain standardisation and regulation -although of general importance- was also explicitly described in a webinar on ISO blockchain governance standardisation.³¹

One of the latest standards regarding governance is IEEE 2145-2023 - Practice for Blockchain Governance. Nevertheless, the ICT Rolling Plan 2025 emphasizes the unchanged priority of this issue:

“(There is) a lack of coherent harmonisation and interoperability that constitute obstacles to cross-border and cross-sector transactions. ... (A) safe and future-proof

³¹ <https://www.ebcc.eu/online-webinar-iso-blockchain-governance-standard/>

technological and regulatory environment, ensuring appropriate interoperability, transparency, accessibility, monitoring and governance (is needed)”.

Regarding the international regulation, the UNCITRAL Model Law on Electronic Transferable Records was mentioned as a role model. Additional regulatory topics are presented in section 4.7.

4.5.3 Data protection

The participants of the public consultation used extensively the opportunity of providing suggestions related to data protection and the GDPR.

As a key issue, the formulated the need for guidance where blockchain/DLT plays a role in GDPR. Specifically, this includes:

- Clarification which HASH calculation procedures are accepted under GDPR;
- Guidance on the hash/encrypted version/ZKP of personal data;
- Guidance on the use and policy for pseudonym identifiers;
- Clarification if a public key is personal data;
- A specification of the meaning of the right to be forgotten in the blockchain context.

Beyond these suggestions, a need for a standard on an "erasable" second blockchain layer ("Layer 2") was formulated. Related with this suggestion, the need for guidance to avoid storing personal data on Layer 1 blockchain / DLT was emphasized.

On this basis, the following action items were derived:

- Develop a GDPR-based guide for blockchain and DLT (already integrated in a broader recommendation of section 4.3.1 as a short-term priority);
- Further analyses of standardisation opportunities regarding an erasable "second" blockchain/DLT layer;

As possible solutions, participants highlighted the guidance by STOA (2019a,b), which could be helpful for further work.

4.6 Long-term priorities

This category includes additional cross-sector topics besides blockchain-based trusted AI, which need to be specified in the following years. Besides considering conclusions of SEEBLOCKS.eu's impact event, it specifically refers to the implication from SEEBLOCKS deliverable D3.3 (Fardad et al., 2024), which highlights that “a multidisciplinary approach to standardisation would be beneficial” because this interoperability issue “often intersects with other emerging technologies such as IoT, 5G, and AI” (p. 21).

This recommendation is also in line with the focus on “Industry verticals (including financial services, robotics), transversal topics (e.g. sustainability) and supporting roles within standardisation” shown in Figure 1. Likewise, it reflects the observation of Beck & Agerskov (2024), that “it is also relevant to consider other technologies that might exist in a blockchain system, such as IoT devices and AI. Digital systems based on multiple types of technologies and autonomous actors must be carefully thought through, lest they result in autonomous systems operating outside human control with the potential to violate societal values and norms”. Therefore, the ethical dimension requires specific consideration in this standardisation context.

4.7 Additional standardisation and policy topics

Participants of the public consultation gave additional suggestions for standardisation and policies in dedicated parts at the beginning and the end of the consultation.

In line with the need for an adjustment of the regulatory framework for DeFi described in section 4.1, the additional **standardisation** topic addresses the foundation **of legally compliant financial transactions**. Rules related to the international Financial Action Task Force (FATF) [Virtual Assets \(fatf-gafi.org\)](https://www.fatf-gafi.org) were also explicitly mentioned in the consultation. The FATF explains the need for action as follows:

“Without proper regulation, virtual assets also risk becoming a safe haven for the financial transactions of criminals and terrorists. The FATF has been closely monitoring developments in the cryptosphere and has issued global, binding standards to prevent the misuse of virtual assets for money laundering and terrorist financing. In recent years, some countries have started to regulate the sector, while others have prohibited virtual assets altogether. However, the majority of countries are yet to implement effective regulations. These gaps in the global regulatory system have created significant loopholes. (...) Countries need to fully and effectively implement the FATF's Standards for virtual assets as a priority.”

As shown by the quotation, the FATF develops its own standards. It also created its own Action Plan to specify Crypto Norms.³² An open question that needs to be clarified regarding the SDOs considered in this report is the extent to which supplementary standardisation work by these organisations could support the FATF in its work. The resulting action item is therefore:

- Analyse potential needs for supplementary standardisation to support the work of the FATF.³³

The additional policy-related suggestions of SEEBLOCKS.eu's consultation refer to new regulatory documents and updates, but also to awareness rising:

- Initiate the necessary steps to facilitate the **legal enforceability** of Smart Contracts;
- Increase **public awareness** initiatives to inform stakeholders about the potential benefits and applications of blockchain technology;
- Check the feasibility of extending the **EU Copyright Directive**, addressing block-chain/DLT-based opportunities to contribute to copyright protection.

The need for guidance regarding the right to be forgotten, already described in section 4.4.3, was also mentioned again.

Another topic, mentioned three times in the public consultation, is "use cases". In line with the ICT Rolling Plan (2025), this topic was also highlighted various times by the speakers of SEEBLOCKS.eu's event series in spring 2025. As this roadmap focusses mainly on specific standardisation and regulatory topics, we decided not to add an additional action item in this context, in addition to their already existing considerations in the ICT Rolling Plan.

In addition, the introduction of EU-wide cryptocurrency taxes was suggested in the consultation. This topic is regarded as being outside the scope of this roadmap and we refer to the relevant European work in the fields of crypto assets and taxation.

4.8 Key players for the roadmap's implementation

Table 6 shows key players related to the roadmap topics. It also represents various topics of specific European interest with established international players but without a clear European voice in standardisation, showing the need for coordination to pursue EU interests more strategically.

³² <https://www.coindesk.com/policy/2023/02/24/fatf-agrees-on-action-plan-to-drive-implementation-of-global-crypto-norms/>

³³ This need for action, which was already emphasized in the preliminary version of this roadmap, was also highlighted in SEEBLOCKS (2025).

Priority	Selected existing stakeholders	Supporting Joining Forces for Blockchain Standardisation & Regulation working groups of various SDOs & additional stakeholders				Comment
		Digital Identity	Smart Contracts	Interop. & CBDC/ Crypto As.	Governance	
Education on BS standardisation (short, medium and long term)	CEN/CENELEC new WG STAIR	x	x	x	x	Mainly a policy topic
Short-Term						
Interoperability and data formats	ISO/TC307/WG7, EBSI			x		Initiation of a CEN-CLC-ETSI JWG on EBSI-related standardisation suggested
Electronic identification and trust services	CEN-CLC/JTC19/WG1, ISO/TC307/JWG4	x				
Decentralised Identity	CEN-CLC/JTC19 WG 1, W3C	x				
Smart Contract security	ISO/TC 307/WG 3		x			
Sustainability and CO ₂ footprint of blockchain	ISO TC307/AG1, WG3, WG6, WG8, CEN-CLC/JTC19/WG2				x	
AI and blockchain (e.g., governance and transparency layer)	ISO/TC307 & JTC1/SC42, CEN-CLC/JTC19 & 21				x	
Medium						
Additional data exchange topics	ISO/TC307/WG6, ITU-T			x		
Data protection	CEN/CENELEC/JTC19 + europ. NSBs					
Long-Term						
Additional cross-technology standardisation topics in the blockchain context	To specified					
Time not specified						
Potential need for supplementary standardisation to support the FATF	ISO/TC307, CEN-CLC JTC 21			x		
Policy and regulatory topics						
Various topics based on chapter 4	Relevant TCs, partly INATBA	x	x	x	x	
		(By an extension of the groups' scope towards the development of recommendations for policy making)				

Note: See also Table 3 regarding key SDOs for the roadmap topics

Table 6: Priorities and suggested responsibilities

Therefore, chapter 3 and 4.4.1 described our recommendation to create Joining Forces for Blockchain Standardisation and Regulation working groups on Smart Contracts, Digital Identity, Governance, Interoperability & CBDC/Crypto Assets. Based on Table 6, these existing stakeholders and new working groups shall be entrusted with the further work on the various priority topics. Potential participants are listed in European Commission and INATBA (2022).

Regarding interoperability and data formats, key players are the international ISO/TC307/WG7 and the European blockchain services infrastructure EBSI, which also provides a development hub and conformance service (<https://hub.ebsi.eu/>). While the participants of the consultation described EBSI-related standardisation needs, EBSI is not yet represented by specific standardisation groups.

Related to ISO/TC307/WG7 as a possible working group where cross-continental interoperability issues could be addressed, the consultation highlighted the importance of the ongoing work on ISO/TS 23516 “Blockchain and Distributed Ledger Technology - Interoperability Framework”.

Additional standardisation activities are needed to specifically consider European needs related to DORA, GDPR, EU Digital Identity and eIDAS2 to develop a guiding standard for security, privacy and access that takes these requirements into account. As an additional measure to support EBSI, a CEN-CLC-ETSI JWG on EBSI-related standardisation is suggested.

Concerning **Electronic identification and trust services (e.g., related to EUDI - eIDAS2)** and the international bridging standard beyond W3C DID and VC, on-going work at ISO/TC307/JWG4 was mentioned. Concerning European standardisation related to eIDAS2, the consultation emphasized the importance of CEN-CENELEC/JTC19/WG1.

Concerning **Decentralised Identity (e.g., SSI, DID, eIDAS2)**, current needs highlight the importance of the EU-led working group suggested in chapter 3.

Regarding **Smart Contracts**, the key TC ISO/TC 307/WG 3 “Smart contracts and their applications” is international. Particular importance of the need for the Joining Forces for Blockchain Standardisation and Regulation working groups on Smart Contracts is seen in the context of the ICT Rolling Plan’s Action 7 of the blockchain chapter to develop standards in line with the Data Act, in particular regarding essential requirements for Smart Contracts.

The key players in most medium-term priority areas are also international TCs. Regarding additional **data exchange** topics, for example, it is ISO/TC307/WG6. In this context the consultation highlighted the relevance of ISO/TC307/WG6’s report ISO/TR 6277 on data flow models for Blockchain / DLT published in February 2024, which already addresses various data exchange aspects. Likewise, ITU-T was referenced regarding standards on blockchain based data sharing and exchange in ITU-T.

The key TC regarding **CO₂ footprint of blockchain** is also international. To support European needs, SEEBLOCKS.eu already supported the creation of a sustainability chapter of ISO TC/307's business plan. Further steps related to the sustainability-related action items of this roadmap shall also be discussed in this regard.

Data protection (e.g., GDPR, EU AI Act) belongs to the topics of CEN/CENELEC/JTC19. Specific additional work with NSBs is suggested regarding the various action items described in the previous sections of chapter 4. The key regulatory standardisation topic of the public consultation was the GDPR. No specific recommendations were given related to the AI Act, but a few suggestions referred to other AI-related topics and are considered separately below.

SEEBLOCKS.eu (2025) added two additional action items in this context, which also address additional stakeholders:

- **GDPR-Driven Privacy Standards:** Define permissioned-network access-control models (RBAC, ABAC) and zero-knowledge proof patterns for on-chain pseudonymity, supporting the ICT Rolling Plan 2025's Action 4 implementations.
- **Data Act Requirements:** Specify normative clauses for smart-contract source-code transparency, standard event-logging formats, and data-sharing interfaces (RESTful/GraphQL APIs) to fulfil Data Act obligations under ICT Rolling Plan 2025 Action 6.

The key TCs related to **AI and blockchain** (e.g., governance and transparency layer on DLT) represent the different domains on EU and international levels. The different stakeholders show the importance of the European working group, which should already start working on short-term priorities.

Besides the research projects described in previous chapters, the key stakeholder regarding education on standardisation and ICT/blockchain standardisation is the new CEN-CENELEC working group, the successor of the former STAIR group.

4.9 Potential barriers and gaps in the implementation of the roadmap and reaction measures

This roadmap presented priorities and related action items for standardisation, numerous SDOs and policy making in the previous sub-chapters. Based on various sources, its implementation faces three potential gaps and barriers in particular:

1. Coordination between various SDOs;
2. Barriers and gaps of specific standardisation projects;
3. Interrelation between standardisation and policy making.

All barriers and relevant reaction measures are shown in Table 7 and explained below.

Gap	Reaction Measures
Coordination between various SDOs	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Establishing working groups like "Joining Forces for Blockchain Standardisation and Regulation" • Actively communicating with target groups to promote coordination
Barriers and gaps related to specific standardisation projects	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Conducting specific evaluation rounds in collaboration with experts and strategy board in the roadmap development • Considering technical constraints in the various project stages
Interrelation between standardisation and policy making	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Submitting key elements to the ICT Rolling Plan 2025 and 2026 • Seeking support from the European Commission • Promoting dialogue between policymakers and standardisation organisations • Involving policy makers in the "Joining Forces for Blockchain Standardisation and Regulation" working groups

Table 7: Potential barriers and gaps in the implementation of the roadmap and reaction measures

While the challenges of **coordinating various SDOs** and the **interrelation between standardisation and policy making** are described in chapters 3 and 4.1, there are **specific barriers and gaps related to each standardisation project**, which are, for example, described by Fomin et al. (2003).

According to Fomin et al. (2003), p. 36 standardization processes include “by necessity (...) the activities of design, sense-making, and negotiation,” Facing various challenges in the different standardisation stages. Regarding the implementation of this roadmap, the elements of sense-making and negotiation in the initiation stage are particularly relevant.

Barriers related to specific standardisation projects are linked with the different stages of the particular (potential) project. Although the standardisation processes of the different standardisation organisations vary, Fomin et al. (2003) distinguish between the general stages Initiation, Requirements discovery, Resource allocation, Specifications development, Standard implementation and Technology introduction based on standard. Likewise, ISO provides a useful practical flowchart as an example, which divides standardisation into six stages: 1) Proposal stage, 2) Preparatory stage, 3) Committee stage, 4) Enquiry stage and 5) Approval stage, followed by 6) the Publication stage, in which the document is published (see ISO, no date).

An important framework condition related to the first stages includes the general priorities of the relevant TC or standardisation group with all experts involved regarding the consideration of new topics and projects. In this context, sense-making means “(c)reating a joint understanding of why a standard is beneficial to different actors (...)” and negotiation “(r)econiling the concept of the standard with incentives of the participating parties.”

After the successful initiation of a new standardisation project, technical constraints may emerge in the various stages. In addition, limitations on the side of the persons involved must be considered, for example concerning time and resources. Various stages, particularly the approval stage require a joint opinion, meaning consensus or a majority decision which can be difficult to reach.

Barriers regarding the **coordination** between different SDOs are addressed by the suggested “Joining Forces for Blockchain Standardisation and Regulation” working groups. Barriers related to the interplay between **standardisation and regulation** are addressed by the suggestion for the groups’ extension to also include regulation.

SEEBLOCKS.eu’s consideration of gaps and barriers related to **the implementation of specific standardisation projects** is mainly related to the first barriers to implementation. The project aimed to address them by actively communicating with its target groups. The concrete suggestions for the roadmap’s focus areas also passed additional evaluation rounds, particularly in collaboration with SEEBLOCKS.eu’s strategy board and additional experts.

An important measure to facilitate further steps for this roadmap has already been taken by submitting key elements as proposed contributions to the ICT Rolling Plan 2025 and 2026. These key elements also included the suggestions for the Joining Forces working groups and were further submitted to the European Commission. If agreement is reached, this will be the first important milestone for the roadmap’s implementation.

5. Summary and next steps

5.1 Roadmap priorities regarding standardisation

This report provided SEEBLOCKS.eu's Blockchain/DLT Standardisation Policy Roadmap. Fundamental topics were discussed in section 3.6 and summarized in Table 4. Based on this basic work and SEEBLOCKS.eu's public consultation, short-, medium- and long-term standardisation priorities were specified.

The **short-term priorities** are the establishment of Joining Forces for Blockchain Standardisation and Regulation working groups, interoperability and data formats, "Electronic identification and trust services (e.g., related to EUDI - eIDAS2)", "Decentralised Identity (e.g., SSI, DID, eIDAS2)" Smart Contract security, and sustainability topics in addition to the already addressed items of the first version of the Blockchain/DLT Standardisation Policy Roadmap and trusted AI.

Medium-term priorities consist of additional data exchange topics and governance policies to support interoperability and data protection.

Long-term priorities refer to additional cross-technology standardisation topics of blockchain besides AI-related issues.

Based on Table 8, this sub-chapter summarizes the specific standardisation needs of the roadmap.

Chapter 3 described the need for Joining Forces for Standardisation working groups to bring the various blockchain stakeholders together. The consultation emphasized the specific interrelations between these groups and the work of policy makers. The **first short-term priority** is therefore the modified action to establish Joining Forces for Standardisation and Regulation working groups that also have a specific focus on dialogues between both domains.

Regarding **interoperability and data formats**, three action items were derived in addition to the ICT Rolling Plan's action item to analyse and if needed, enhance the interoperability and international compatibility of the current and pending EBSI topics and capabilities:

- Initiate the development of interoperability standards for SSI and DIDs in collaboration with key stakeholders from the SSI and DID areas (see also the separate section on decentralized identity);
- Develop guidelines for security, privacy and access that specifically consider the European requirements of DORA, GDPR, EU Digital Identity, eIDAS2;
- Further analyse and address the needs for additional standards for data formats, data exchange and data portability according to current needs.

Standardisation and broader policy-based support for blockchain and DLT technologies

Standardisation

Short-Term: starting 2025	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Joining Forces for Blockchain Standardisation and Regulation working groups • Guiding standard for security, privacy and access that specifically considers the European requirements of DORA, GDPR, EU Digital Identity, eIDAS2 • Interoperability and data formats • Electronic identification and trust services (e.g., related to EUDI - eIDAS2) • Decentralised Identity (e.g., SSI, DID, eIDAS2) • Smart Contract security • Sustainability and safety for consumers, standards towards assessing environmental and sustainability impact including, in particular, CO₂ footprint and energy consumption of different blockchains/DLTs, MiCA, EU Sustainable Finance taxonomy¹ • Blockchain-supported trusted AI 	
Medium-Term: starting 2027	Long-Term: starting 2027+
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Additional needs regarding data formats and data exchange • Additional data protection topics 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Needs for additional² cross-technology standardisation topics in the blockchain context, also with specific consideration of ethical aspects
<p>¹ Updated priority based on the ICT Rolling Plan 2025, replacing the sustainability priority of this report's first version, which is already considered by the time of this report's completion</p> <p>² In addition to blockchain and AI</p>	

Broader policy-based support

Short-term priorities
<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Joining Forces for Blockchain Standardisation and Regulation" working groups 2. Legal validity and enforceability of Smart Contracts 3. DID policies and suitable regulatory framework conditions to support the interoperability between DIDs 4. Support education on blockchain standardisation
Medium-term priorities
<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Suitable regulatory framework conditions for blockchain governance 2. Regulatory support for trusted registries 3. Additional regulatory measures for Decentralised Finance 4. Sustainability framework 5. Specify standardisation education, analyse updated education needs
Long-term priorities
<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Adjust blockchain and ICT standardisation education strategies

Note: a more detailed version of these tables is included in the executive summary of this report

Table 8: Short, medium & long-term priorities for standardisation and policies to support blockchain & DLT according to Table 5

Related to the first two action items, a specific need for standardisation bridging DIDs beyond the ongoing international (W3C) work by also considering the European specificities such as the eIDAS2 regulation was became obvious. This finding also stresses the observation of BITKOM (2023) that an additional issue regarding internationally interoperable systems beyond eIDAS exist.

Concerning **electronic identification and trust services**, BITKOM (2023) highlighted likewise that an inclusion of an international perspective beyond eIDAS 2.0 in the governance of SSI is needed. They added that SSI offers interesting opportunities to think about security features in new ways but also brings challenges.

Additional key action items related to this topic area are according to the current consultation:

- Initiate the creation of a European standard framework for blockchain / DLT solution for EU Digital Identity Wallet (EUDIW);
- Work on the creation of signature standards on blockchains and standards for oracles;
- Initiate a CEN-CLC-ETSI JWG on EBSI-related standardisation;
- Analyse suitable topics for further standardisation measures to support EBSI and initiate appropriate follow-up measures;

- Analyse the needs for sector-specific standards related to EBSI specifically;
- Further analyse standardisation needs related to DPKI and implement appropriate follow-up measures;
- Further check the needs for qualified Electronic Ledger certification processes and guidelines.

As mentioned in the section on interoperability, the key action items concerning **Decentralised Identity (e.g., SSI, DID, eIDAS2)** are mainly related to interoperability:

- Further work on DID interoperability; Initiate standardisation bridging DIDs and Blockchain / DLT beyond W3C's work by also considering the European specificities including the eIDAS2 regulation;
- Further work on SSI interoperability standardisation, specifically that a credential managed by EUDIW can be recognized by other SSI systems from other regions ("transatlantic" wallet interoperability);

Action items related to "**Smart Contract security**" include standards for audits and security metrics and Oracle standardisation.

In addition to the high-priority standardisation issues related to **data formats and data exchange**, participants also indicated the need for medium-term standardisation support in this context, but the suggestions were very general. Based on the short-term measures of further analysing and addressing the needs for additional standards for data formats, data exchange and data portability according to current needs, specific follow-up steps have to be specified.

Governance-related policies to support interoperability are also regarded as medium-term priority. BITKOM (2023) already described that sovereign, SSI-based documents require a new type of governance. In addition, the ICT Rolling Plan 2024, Action 7 (2025: Action 6) recommended to explore a general framework for Governance of the European networks based on DLT to allow the flow of Smart Contracts between different networks. Participants of SEEBLOCKS's consultation described the importance of implementing coherent global regulations for blockchain governance, repeating various statements of ISO/TC307/WG5 and highlighting the importance of implementing appropriate relations between standardisation and regulation in this respect.

The key action items related to **data protection** are the development of a GDPR-based guiding standard for blockchain and DLT and further analyses of standardisation opportunities regarding an erasable second blockchain/DLT layer. As possible solutions for the various data protection issues, participants mentioned the guidance provided by STOA (2019a,b). As mentioned in section 3, a European standardisation project considering **DIN SPEC 4997:2020-04** has already started by the time of this roadmap's completion.

Regarding **sustainability**, the public consultation unveiled the vision of a “worldwide standard for designing sustainable Blockchain / DLT systems and for assessing and monitoring the environmental footprint” based on already started standardisation activities. Specifically, participants mentioned consistent measurements and standards to calculate the CO₂ footprint of each transaction (if not yet addressed by the time of this roadmap’s implementation). They also emphasized specific needs related to eIDAS2 and the need for broader sustainability analyses regarding electric consumption, carbon footprint / CO₂ emission, water footprint and electronic waste. In line with the ICT Rolling Plan 2025, this roadmap specified further measures, which already go beyond narrow CO₂ footprint topics.

Regarding **Artificial Intelligence and blockchain** new needs for action communicated by various stakeholders in different contexts were specified. The consultation also highlighted the various parties, for whom considerations on the CO₂ footprint are relevant, e.g. ISO TC/307 WPGs 3, 6, 8, which requires coordination. The suggested specific working group could be considered by TC307/AG1 regarding an integration in the strategic business plan. However, to consider specific European interests, the creation of a European WG is suggested, e.g., consisting of European participants of WGs 3, 6 and 8.

Various recommendations also referred to regulation, particularly regarding the question what CO₂ footprint (per block) is acceptable. The above-mentioned standardisation activities can help support its practical implementation. The internalization of the environmental cost was also considered in this context.

Further analyses are suggested regarding potential new cross-technological standardisation needs for the next years. An additional action item related to standardisation refers to an analysis of potential needs for **supplementary standardisation to support the work of the FATF**.

5.2 Roadmap priorities for policy support

The various suggestions for policy support in chapter 4 can be summarized by the following topics:

Short-Term priorities starting 2025:

1. Join the standards community in establishing joining forces for standards and regulation working groups that also have a specific focus on dialogues between standardisation and regulation;
2. Specify requirements for legal validity and enforceability of **Smart Contracts**, further work on additional needs regarding the legal recognition of DLTs and DLT-based solutions;
3. Develop **DID policies**, also supporting the interoperability between DIDs;

4. Support education on blockchain standardisation also considering IWA 30

Medium-Term priorities starting 2027:

1. Provide suitable regulatory framework conditions for blockchain governance by considering the suggested guiding standard for security, privacy and access that specifically considers the European requirements of DORA, GDPR, EU Digital Identity, eIDAS2;
2. Further care for **trusted registries**: further analyse the needs for regulatory support and improvements in the regulatory framework conditions;
3. Check needs for additional regulatory measures for **Decentralised Finance** besides international FATF regulation;
4. Specify the **sustainability framework** for blockchain including acceptable CO₂ footprints and rules for covering environmental cost;
5. Specify standardisation education by also considering the final results of the EDU4Standards.eu project and analyse updated education needs.

Long-Term priority starting 2027+: Adjust blockchain and ICT standardisation education strategies, e.g. within the project StandICT 2029.

Variable priority: Check the feasibility of extending the EU Copyright Directive, addressing blockchain/DLT-based opportunities to contribute to copyright protection.

A key goal and action item refers to the above-mentioned establishment of Joining Forces for Blockchain Standardisation and Regulation working groups **(1)** that also have a specific focus on dialogues between standardisation and regulation. While various policy makers already have established ties to the standardisation communities and specific TCs, additional work is necessary at EU and Member State level to engage suitable experts to participate in these groups. Examples for the interrelation between standardisation and policy making are provided by the experts who were involved in “Joining Forces for Blockchain Standardisation” in 2021, see European Commission and INATBA (2022).

The legal validity of Smart Contracts and the legal recognition of DLT and DLT-based solutions in general **(2)** shall be facilitated by the development of appropriate standards. Likewise, DID policies **(3)**, regulatory measures for DeFi **(6)** and the development of the sustainability framework **(7)** are related to standardisation.

Standardisation promoting policy making by providing references regarding DeFi **(6)** should refer to the work of the international Financial Action Task Force (FATF). Likewise, the specification of acceptable CO₂ footprints **(7)** should be based on standardized values.

The recommendations to develop suitable regulatory framework conditions for blockchain governance **(4)** and the sustainability framework **(7)** are linked with specific recommendations for standardisation in chapter 5.1 and emphasise the importance of close interrelations between blockchain standardisation and regulation and the establishment of the establishing joining forces for standards and regulation working groups. While the regulatory framework should specifically consider European views on security, privacy and access, the development of the sustainability framework **(7)** should consider the specification of acceptable CO₂ footprints based on standardized values, guidance regarding an internalization of the environmental cost.

Trusted registries **(5)** represent a key goal related to EBSI.³⁴ Further needs for regulatory support should be analysed in this context. Targeted analyses are also suggested regarding the feasibility of an extension of the EU Copyright Directive **(8)**.

Additional suggestions for the development of policy recommendations refer to **public awareness** to inform stakeholders about the potential benefits and applications of blockchain technology and the consideration of **additional research projects to support the standardisation measures and/or regulatory sandboxes**.

As another helpful measure, **EBSI** would benefit from an overview of business requirements and insight how and where this infrastructure can help businesses. Specifically, a framework for business capability identification and mapping could be useful.

5.3 Current impact of SEEBLOCKS.eu's roadmap and outlook

SEEBLOCKS.eu's Blockchain/DLT Standardisation Policy Roadmap drafted goals, action items, priorities and timelines. It also discussed gaps, barriers and countermeasures.

Specific needs for standardisation and policy-based support were identified in SEEBLOCKS.eu's public consultation and are represented by the roadmap's central action items. The topics are categorised according to short, medium and long-term priorities and assigned to the responsibility of various stakeholders.

From the beginning, SEEBLOCKS has aimed to contribute to the EU Rolling Plan for ICT Standardisation, which is summarized in Figure 10.

³⁴ See <https://ec.europa.eu/digital-building-blocks/sites/display/EBSI/EBSI+a+new+trust+paradigm+for+Web3>

The EU Rolling Plan for ICT Standardisation

The Rolling Plan for ICT Standardisation provides a unique bridge between EU policies and standardisation activities concerning information and communication technologies (ICT).

Standardisation actions identified in the Rolling Plan to support EU policies are complementary to other instruments, in particular the Annual Union Work Programme (AUWP).

Major element of the implementation of the European Standardisation Strategy

Lists all known areas where ICT standardisation could support EU policy objectives

Details the requirements for ICT standardisation, translates them into actions and providing a follow-up mechanism for the actions

Result of an annual dialogue involving a wide-range of interested parties as represented by the European multi-stakeholder platform on ICT standardisation (MSP)

Regularly updated on an annual basis

Focus on actions

Addresses the global ICT standardisation community

DLT and the EU Rolling Plan for ICT Standardisation | Jochen Friedrich

11

Source: Friedrich (2025)

Figure 10: Overview of the ICT Rolling Plan

Contributions for this plan are collected each spring and SEEBLOCKS.eu could contribute two times to this process. Based on early findings for the roadmap's preliminary version, the project could already share first results. On this basis, SEEBLOCKS.eu contributed particularly to the following recommendation of the Rolling Plan's 2025 edition based on early findings for the first version of this report, presented in the first chapters there:

“Action 2: Continue identifying use cases which are relevant for EU (including EU regulatory requirements like from GDPR, AI Act, Data Act, ePrivacy, eIDAS, AMLD, TOOP, CSRD, etc.) also leveraging on the yearly event “Joining Forces for Blockchain Standardisation” co-organised by the European Commission and INATBA (...) with special focus on Smart Contracts, Digital Identity, Governance, Interoperability, CBDC/Crypto Assets; submit them to standardisation bodies, including CEN & CENELEC and ETSI, and also ISO, ITU.”

After its completion, the year 1 edition of this report was sent to the MSP in autumn 2024 to be considered in the preparation of the 2026 edition, starting in spring 2025. The next steps in this context are described in Figure 11.

Source: Friedrich (2025)

Figure 11: Important dates of the EU's ICT Rolling Plan 2026

An important additional recommendation is the inclusion of specific action items related to standardisation education in the Rolling Plan as outlined in section 1. The EU project EDU4Standards.eu will develop a detailed policy roadmap in this context. SEEBLOCKS.eu's suggestions related to blockchain were already sent to the project.

In parallel to this report, SEEBLOCKS is finalising the additional Landscape Report D3.6 (SEEBLOCKS.eu, 2025), which describe additional blockchain standardisation gaps. While it addresses various stakeholders, we also recommend considering these gaps in the new StandICT.2029 project. Members of this future project were already contacted and will be provided with the relevant documents.

SEEBLOCKS.eu envisions a future where blockchain is not only a transformative technology, but a trusted foundation for digital sovereignty, transparency, and innovation across Europe and beyond. As the global landscape races to define the rules of tomorrow's digital connected world, Europe has a historic opportunity and a responsibility to lead. By shaping open, inclusive, and interoperable blockchain standards, Europe can ensure that this powerful technology aligns with its values: privacy, security, sustainability, and democratic governance, and spread to other major democratic regions across the globe, for a strong and well-balanced digital age.

The Rolling Plan for ICT Standardisation offers a vital policy instrument to coordinate these efforts and to align blockchain standardisation with Europe's broader digital goals—ensuring coherence, continuity, and high-impact results. SEEBLOCKS.eu is dedicated to bring a strong voice into these plans, by providing united inputs from stakeholders (e.g. startups, SDOs, academia, public institutions) that will accelerate the development and adoption of blockchain standards that are resilient, inclusive, and future-proof.

References

Beck, R. & Agerskov, S. (Eds.). (2024). Ethical Guidelines for Blockchain Systems. Copenhagen, Denmark: European Blockchain Center. [https://blockchain-observatory.ec.europa.eu/document/download/f74bb2b0-4524-4134-ab52-e25a0bcd9b7c_en?filename=Ethical Guidelines for Blockchain Systems.pdf](https://blockchain-observatory.ec.europa.eu/document/download/f74bb2b0-4524-4134-ab52-e25a0bcd9b7c_en?filename=Ethical%20Guidelines%20for%20Blockchain%20Systems.pdf)

BITKOM (2023). Effiziente Identitätsverwaltung: Einblicke in SSI, DLT und KYC-Prozesse. <https://www.bitkom.org/sites/main/files/2023-10/bitkom-thesenpapier-effiziente-identitaetsverwaltung.pdf>

Blind, K., et al. (2018). Publishing, patenting, and standardisation: Motives and barriers of scientists, *Research Policy*, 47(7), 1185-1197

Blind, K., et al. (2022). Motives to Publish, to Patent and to Standardize: An Explorative Study Based on Individual Engineers' Assessments, *Technological Forecasting and Social Change*, 175, 121420

Blind, K., & Gauch, S. (2009). Research and standardisation in nanotechnology: evidence from Germany. *J Technol Transf*, 34(3), 320-342.

Blind, K., & Heß, P. (2023). Stakeholder perceptions of the role of standards for addressing the sustainable development goals, *Sustainable Production and Consumption*, 37, 180-190.

Blind, K., & von Laer, M. (2022). Paving the path: drivers of standardisation participation at ISO. *J Technol Transf* 47, 1115–1134.

Blockchain Bundesverband (2025). "Trusted AI" – ein Modell für Europa. Wie die Kombination von Blockchain und AI mehr Vertrauen in zukünftige Anwendungen künstlicher Intelligenz herstellen kann. Ein Aufruf an Politik, Wirtschaft und Gesellschaft / Berlin, 15. Januar 2025, <https://bundesblock.de/trusted-ai-ein-modell-fuer-europa/>

CEN-CLC (2020). CEN-CENELEC Road Map Report on AI, version 2020-09. https://www.cenelec.eu/media/CEN-CENELEC/AreasOfWork/CEN-CENELEC_Topics/Artificial%20Intelligence/Quicklinks%20General/Documentation%20and%20Materials/cen-clc_fgreport_roadmap_ai.pdf

CEN-CLC (2022). CEN/CLC/JTC 19/WG 01 Decentralised identity management https://standards.cenelec.eu/dyn/www/f?p=205:7:0:::FSP_ORG_ID:2935523&cs=1FD8E28605C868918FE6DCAC943F90338

Chainlink (2024). What Is a Blockchain Oracle? <https://chain.link/education/blockchain-oracles>

Delaney, F. (2023). D3.1 Blockchain and DLT standardisation landscape report. <https://zenodo.org/records/10797789>

Delaney, F., Farrell, S., & Favaro, J. (2024). D3.2 Report of results of the early public consultation. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10698542>

DIF (2024). Decentralized identity leaders partner to accelerate DID method standardization. <https://blog.identity.foundation/decentralized-identity-leaders-partner-to-accelerate-did-method-standardization/>

DIN, DKE (2022). German Standardization Roadmap on Artificial Intelligence (2nd edition). www.din.de/go/roadmap-ai

EBCC (2022). Online Webinar: ISO Blockchain Governance Standard. <https://www.ebcc.eu/online-webinar-iso-blockchain-governance-standard/>

Edler, J., et al. (2023). Technology Sovereignty as an Emerging Frame for Innovation Policy. Defining Rationales, Ends and Means. Research Policy

ETSI (2023). ETSI Involvement in AI. <https://portal.etsi.org/TB-SiteMap/OCG/OCG-AI-Co-ordination>

EUDI Wallet (2024). European Digital Identity Wallet Architecture and Reference Framework. <https://eu-digital-identity-wallet.github.io/eudi-doc-architecture-and-reference-framework/1.4.0/arf/>

European Commission (2022). COM(2022) 68 final. 2022/0047(COD) Proposal for a REGULATION OF THE EUROPEAN PARLIAMENT AND OF THE COUNCIL on harmonised rules on fair access to and use of data (Data Act). (Text with EEA relevance) {SEC(2022) 81 final} - {SWD(2022) 34 final} - {SWD(2022) 35 final}. <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=COM%3A2022%3A68%3AFIN>

European Commission (2023). Blockchain Strategy. <https://digital-strategy.ec.europa.eu/en/policies/blockchain-strategy>

European Commission (2021). COMMISSION RECOMMENDATION (EU) 2021/946 of 3 June 2021 on a common Union Toolbox for a coordinated approach towards a European Digital Identity Framework, OJ L 210/51, 14.6.2021. https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=uriserv:OJ.L_.2021.210.01.0051.01.ENG

European Commission (2022). COM(2022) 31 final. COMMUNICATION FROM THE COMMISSION TO THE EUROPEAN PARLIAMENT, THE COUNCIL, THE EUROPEAN ECONOMIC AND SOCIAL COMMITTEE AND THE COMMITTEE OF THE REGIONS. An EU Strategy on Standardisation. Setting global standards in support of a resilient, green and digital EU single market. [COM 2022 31 1 EN ACT part1 v5.pdf](#)

European Commission (2023). Rolling Plan for ICT standardisation. Blockchain and Distributed Digital Ledger Technologies (RP2023). <https://interoperable-europe.ec.europa.eu/>

[collection/rolling-plan-ict-standardisation/blockchain-and-distributed-digital-ledger-technologies-rp2023](#)

European Commission (2024a). Rolling Plan for ICT standardisation. Blockchain and Distributed Digital Ledger Technologies (RP2024). <https://joinup.ec.europa.eu/collection/rolling-plan-ict-standardisation/blockchain-and-distributed-digital-ledger-technologies-rp2024>

European Commission (2024b). Rolling Plan for ICT standardisation. Artificial Intelligence (RP2024). <https://joinup.ec.europa.eu/collection/rolling-plan-ict-standardisation/artificial-intelligence-rp2024>

European Commission (2025). Rolling Plan for ICT standardisation. Blockchain and Distributed Digital Ledger Technologies (RP2025). <https://interoperable-europe.ec.europa.eu/collection/rolling-plan-ict-standardisation/blockchain-and-distributed-digital-ledger-technologies-rp2025>.

European Commission and INATBA (2022). Joining Forces for Blockchain Standardisation 2021 - Event Report. <https://digital-strategy.ec.europa.eu/en/library/joining-forces-blockchain-standardisation-2021-event-report>

European Parliament and the Council (2023a). REGULATION (EU) 2023/1114 OF THE EUROPEAN PARLIAMENT AND OF THE COUNCIL of 31 May 2023 on markets in crypto-assets, and amending Regulations (EU) No 1093/2010 and (EU) No 1095/2010 and Directives 2013/36/EU and (EU) 2019/1937 (Text with EEA relevance). <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/DE/TXT/?uri=CELEX%3A32023R1114>

European Parliament and the Council (2023b). Regulation (EU) 2023/2854 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 13 December 2023 on harmonised rules on fair access to and use of data and amending Regulation (EU) 2017/2394 and Directive (EU) 2020/1828 (Data Act). <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/eli/reg/2023/2854>

European Parliament and of the Council (2024). Regulation (EU) 2024/1183 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 11 April 2024 amending Regulation (EU) No 910/2014, <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/eli/reg/2024/1183/oj>

Fardad, M., Tal, I., Delaney, F., Farrell, S. (2024). D3.3 Landscape and gap analysis report on Blockchain/DLT standardisation – Mid-term rel.

Fomin, V., Keil, T., Lyytinen, K. (2008). Theorizing about Standardization: Integrating Fragments of Process Theory in Light of Telecommunication Standardization Wars All Sprouts Content. 45. http://aisel.aisnet.org/sprouts_all/45

Friedrich, J. (2025). EU Policy objectives for Distributed Ledgers Technologies: The EU Rolling Plan for ICT Standardisation. SEEBLOCKS.eu Impact Event. Brussels. 10 April 2025. IEA (2014). *Energy*

Technology Roadmaps: A Guide to Development and Implementation, IEA Technology Roadmaps, IEA, Paris, <https://doi.org/10.1787/9789264086340-en>

INATBA (2024). DLT Standardisation: A Comprehensive Report on Current Efforts and Future Directions. <https://inatba.org/reports/dlt-standardisation-a-comprehensive-report-on-current-efforts-and-future-directions/>

ISO (no date). Voting and membership in ISO. https://www.iso.org/sites/ConsumersStandards/voting_iso.html

ISO (2019). Competence of standards professionals Part 1: In companies. <https://www.iso.org/standard/75875.html>

ISO (2021). Standards & economic growth: ISO members' research on the impact of standards on their national economies, Geneva 2021

Pohlmann, N. (2024). Self-Sovereign Identity (SSI). <https://norbert-pohlmann.com/glossar-cyber-sicherheit/self-sovereign-identity-ssi/>

SEEBLOCKS.eu (2024). D3.5 Report of results of the second-iteration public consultation

SEEBLOCKS.eu (2025). D3.6 Landscape and gap analysis report on Blockchain/DLT standardisation – Final release

STOA (2019a). Blockchain and the General Data Protection Regulation. Can distributed ledgers be squared with European data protection law? STUDY. Panel for the Future of Science and Technology. [https://www.europarl.europa.eu/RegData/etudes/STUD/2019/634445/EPRS_STU\(2019\)634445_EN.pdf](https://www.europarl.europa.eu/RegData/etudes/STUD/2019/634445/EPRS_STU(2019)634445_EN.pdf)

STOA (2019b). STOA Options Brief. Blockchain and the General Data Protection Regulation. Can distributed ledgers be squared with European data protection law? [https://www.europarl.europa.eu/RegData/etudes/STUD/2019/634445/EPRS_STU\(2019\)634445\(ANN1\)_EN.pdf](https://www.europarl.europa.eu/RegData/etudes/STUD/2019/634445/EPRS_STU(2019)634445(ANN1)_EN.pdf)

Swann, P. (2010). International Standards and Trade: A Review of the Empirical Literature", OECD Trade Policy Papers, No. 97, OECD Publishing

W3C (2022). Decentralized Identifiers (DIDs) v1.0. Core architecture, data model, and representations. W3C Recommendation 19 July 2022. <https://www.w3.org/TR/did-core/>

W3C (2023). Decentralized Identifier Working Group Charter. <https://w3c.github.io/did-wg-charter/>

Annex 1: Roadmap Questionnaire of the Open Consultation

THE FUTURE BLOCKCHAIN AND DLT STANDARDISATION PUBLIC CONSULTATION

The [EU Standardisation Rolling Plan 2023](#) identifies Blockchain and DLT as a key vector for innovation in the Digital Single Market providing an infrastructure for trusted, decentralised and dis-intermediated services beyond the financial sector. This public consultation seeks to capture key priorities for industry in the development of this important infrastructure and to better understand where emerging standards can lend support and value.

Gender

Country

Organisation Type

Technology Area you are working in

Please select a maximum of 3 options

Have you contributed to the work of any SDOs listed below?

3GPP	IEEE	OPC
APTA	IEC	O-RAN
ARIB	IETF	SAE
ASTM	IHE	SIS
ATIS	iiRDS	SMPTE
BSI	INCITS	SNIA
CEN	ISACA	SPC
CENELEC	ISO	TIA
CEN/CENELEC	ISO/IEC	TSDSI
CSA	ITU	TTA
CWL	NEMA	TTC
DIN	NIST	UL
DMTF	OAGi	UN/CEFACT
DOD	OASIS	UNI
DS	ODCA	W3C/ERCIM
ECMA	OGF	I haven't contributed.
ETSI	OMG	Other...
GICTF	ON	
HL7	oneM2M	

Have you contributed to protocol development on any blockchains listed below? Eg through public Request for Comments (RFCs) consensus process?

Alastria	Cudos	Polygon
Algorand	EBSI	Quant
Binance	Ethereum	Solana
Bitcoin	Hyperledger	Tezos
Cardano	LACNet	I haven't contributed.
Chainlink	ONTOCHAIN	Other...
Cosmos	Polkadot	

(excluded here: Fundamental questions used for other SEEBLOCKS.eu tasks)

ROADMAP

Please classify the following blockchain and adjacent standardisation topics as short, medium and long-term priorities:

You can submit up to 3 options per category (up to 3 short-term, up to 3 long-term).

Interoperability between different blockchain networks	Short	Medium	Long
Smart Contract Security	Short	Medium	Long
Artificial Intelligence and blockchain (eg. governance and transparency layer on DLT)	Short	Medium	Long
CO ₂ footprint of blockchain and other high-compute services (eg Quantum computing, Training AI models)	Short	Medium	Long
Data exchange (eg. eIDAS2, SWIFT)	Short	Medium	Long
Data protection (eg. GDPR, EU AI ACT)	Short	Medium	Long
Electronic identification and trust services (e.g., related to EUDI – eIDAS2)	Short	Medium	Long
Decentralised Identity (eg. SSI, DID, eIDAS2)	Short	Medium	Long

Please specify the standardisation needs briefly

The following action items related to interoperability were mentioned at SEEBLOCKS.eu's first public consultation. Please rate the importance of each item (high, middle or low).

Governance models to enable interoperability across the tech stack
(Cloud Computing, Peer to Peer computing, Edge and fog computing) High Middle Low

Standards for data formats and Interoperability
(eIDAS2, SWIFT) High Middle Low

Guidelines for security, privacy and access
(DORA, GDPR, EU Digital Identity, eIDAS2) High Middle Low

Are there interoperability problems of blockchain/DLT between the EU, the U.S. and Asia that could be addressed by standardisation?

- Yes
- No
- Don't know

Which additional measures should be undertaken by regulation (law) or voluntary standardisation (by the industry and other stakeholders) to support the interoperability of blockchain/DLT?

By regulation

By creating voluntary standards

Are there specific blockchain-related standardisation needs in relation to data protection and Europe's General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR)?

- Yes
- No
- Don't know

Is there a need for specific blockchain-related AI (artificial intelligence) standards or regulation?

- Yes
- No
- Don't know

Are there needs for standards and/or regulations in the following areas to support blockchain/DLT?

CO₂ footprint of blockchain

- Yes
- No

Data exchange

- Yes
- No

Electronic identification and trust services (EUDI – eIDAS2)

- Yes
- No

Decentralised Identifiers (DIDs) in Smart Contracts

- Yes
- No

Which additional regulatory/policy support is needed for blockchain/DLT technologies?

If you have any further suggestions regarding blockchain/DLT technologies, standardisation and regulation or the SEEBLOCKS.eu project, please include them here.

Annex 2: Answers of the Open Consultation

Interoperability problems of blockchain/DLT between the EU, the U.S. and Asia that could be addressed by standardisation

Interoperability problems
data exchange
Data portability and identity management.
Mainly at the governance level (legal recognition of blockchain-based solutions)
Regulatory issues that could be addressed by standardization and consistency of laws, particularly in regulation of exchanges and securities, and privacy and data protection.
See my previous response ("transatlantic" wallet interoperability)
Possible solutions
ISO/TC307/WG7 is a possible working group where these cross-continental interoperability issues could be addressed (e.g. within on-going ISO/TS 23516)
Additional comments
Application of regulation between these geographic regions - application data flows are crucial
Due to different regulatory and policy issues among countries
Every protocol has a different interactions and operating model.
The EU projects on-going is pointing in the right direction regarding digital identity, but need to result in standards and SW developer frameworks soon.
Defining EU standards and profiles will facilitate such interoperability
Each party wants to create its own standard and defend it, different standards - interoperability issues
There are widely known interoperability issues in blockchain solutions, as those solutions are mostly isolated and not widely implemented, especially across regions.

Various suggestions for regulatory measures or standardisation to support blockchain interoperability

Suggestions for regulatory measures
EIDAS2 regulation
eIDAS review defined trusted Ledger. Interoperability (that is mostly not technical) shall also be regulated.
DEFI regulation
Consistency of regulation of exchanges and broker/dealer rules, consistency of securities laws, and consistency of privacy/data protection/identity laws.
Standardisation of processes that would lead to legal recognition of DLTs and DLT-based solutions
Federated identity
A more restrictive approach to applying the GDPR when encryption measures are integrated.
More focus should be put on enabling various regulatory sandboxes.
the common use of decentralized oracles
legal validity of smart contracts
Requirements to use new digital tools for automating mandatory reporting already in place.
regulatory compliance support
Create prioritisation and urgency towards investment in correct security tools for the current gaps.
Funding SMALL projects to create domain-specific semantic catalogues for attributes/ credentials
to accept public blockchains for DLT services accepted by eIDAS 2.0
Additional comments
More discussion and experience-learning from real-life use cases (...).
Regulation is not likely to work.
ISO TC 307 WG 7 is working on Blockchain interoperability
Region-wide and inter-regional blockchain developments should be supported by either regulation or standardization. System Communication should be standardized to enable seamless inter-system communication, (e.g.) for retrieving/sending data from/to ERP systems.
It would probably not be possible to mandate by regulation a particular blockchain platform for a particular purpose. Only by reference to an International Standard will that be possible.
Provide ready-to-use platform
EU Regulation: recommendation not to ban any blockchain / DLT system
Travel Rule (FATF) (regrouped)

Suggestions for standards
data transfer
Identity formats (may require regulation) Data formats and data exchange Smart contract security Governance
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - security - identification (legal entity and natural person identity) - authentication - data exchange
Interoperability between DIDs is the key, and maybe some harmonization on the trusted registries, as each identity model defines it different
Interoperability standards / DID standards
Federated identity
Particularly around auditing.
the common use of decentralized oracles
rulebooks by industry verticals
See before, as an output of a funded project
to use/accept commercial wallets to store data like google or apple wallet
Possible solutions
ISO TS will be available soon
Standardisation: publish ISO/TS 23516
Additional comments
Voluntary means exceptions (so bilateral agreements)
There is a need for general blockchain platform like Hyperledger Fabric developed by an International Standardization organization, such as ISO or ITU-T (ITU-T Study Group 17 has a group working on blockchain).
Focus on globally and commonly acceptable standards and then develop specific standards according to different regulatory issues
'Voluntary standards allow for greater flexibility and adaptability on the part of the industry, fostering innovation and collaboration between different actors in the blockchain ecosystem, as well as allowing for the introduction of aspects that can only be established by sector, such as: the relevance of the data entered into the system, transparency on governance conditions or consensus mechanisms'. (Translated)

General suggestions regarding the short-, medium- & long-term priorities

Interoperability
Standardisation of external interfaces and processes that allow users to easily interconnect and be interoperable. One notable example to look at is the EBSI dev hub and conformance service, that played a key role in SSI evolution in EU (https://hub.ebsi.eu/). Having stable profiles for standards, conformance testing, and stakeholder management are key for adoption. (see also section Decentralised Identity (e.g. SSI, DID, eIDAS2))
How a credential managed by EUDIW could be recognized by another SSI system that works in another region? ("transatlantic" wallet interoperability). Recognized means: ascertain its validity in the origin SSI and make it legally binding in the other (see also section Decentralised Identity (e.g. SSI, DID, eIDAS2))
Key needs around interoperability and security, particularly through adopting standards that can facilitate auditing.
Interoperability between blockchains at protocol level will be practically impossible, but easier at DID level. The problem is that DID is not a good standard for interoperability, so some standardization work here must be done to add interoperability features. (see also section Decentralised Identity (e.g. SSI, DID, eIDAS2))
Challenge: The lack of interoperability between different blockchain platforms creates "digital islands" that cannot effectively communicate with each other (Trade Finance Global), (RAND Analysis). Solution: Develop global standards to ensure interoperability among diverse platforms, facilitating connectivity and collaboration across various industries and regions.
Electronic identification and trust services (e.g., related to EUDI - eIDAS2)
Electronic Identification & Trust Services + Decentralised Identity: 1) A worldwide standard bridging Decentralised Identifier / Identity and Blockchain / DLT beyond W3C DID and VC (on-going work at ISO/TC307/JWG4) and a European standard covering the European specificities including eIDAS2 regulation (on-going work at CEN-CENELEC/JTC19/WG1); 2) A European standard framework for blockchain / DLT solutions for EU Digital Identity Wallet (EUDIW)
Association between identity and public key Third-party management of the private key Global time assertions On-chain data semantics Off-chain data feeds Verifiability (...)
Build-in identity management and access control should also be a design objective.

Decentralised Identity (e.g. SSI, DID, eIDAS2)
Identity - Standards for creation, issuance, and storage of decentralized identity, and compatibility between standards.
Electronic Identification & Trust Services + Decentralised Identity: 1) A worldwide standard bridging Decentralised Identifier / Identity and Blockchain / DLT beyond W3C DID and VC (on-going work at ISO/TC307/JWG4) and a European standard covering the European specificities including eIDAS2 regulation (on-going work at CEN-CENELEC/JTC19/WG1); 2) A European standard framework for blockchain / DLT solutions for EU Digital Identity Wallet (EUDIW)
Standardisation of external interfaces and processes that allow users to easily interconnect and be interoperable. One notable example to look at is the EBSI dev hub and conformance service, that played a key role in SSI evolution in EU (https://hub.ebsi.eu/). Having stable profiles for standards, conformance testing, and stakeholder management are key for adoption. (see also section on interoperability)
How a credential managed by EUDIW could be recognized by another SSI system that works in another region? ("transatlantic" wallet interoperability). Recognized means: ascertain its validity in the origin SSI and make it legally binding in the other (see also section on interoperability)
Interoperability between blockchains at protocol level will be practically impossible, but easier at DID level. The problem is that DID is not a good standard for interoperability, so some standardization work here must be done to add interoperability features. (see also section on interoperability)
Smart contracts
Smart contract security - Standards for audits and security metrics.
Smart contract security must be part of any blockchain standardization activity. (...)
Oracle Standardization
Data exchange
Which is the semantic data catalogue to exchange attributes? How do you model attributes like financial data for legal persons, organizational structure, power of attorney, education data? How to make a credential that is machine readable?
CO2 footprint
Standards for measurement of energy used, impact of renewables, hardware impact, etc.
CO2 footprint: Minimising the use of resources, in particular electricity, should have a major design goal. Use of compact syntax tools that produces short messages (no XML). Avoid unnecessary complexity, use effective consensus protocol.
Energy consumption

CO₂ Footprint: A worldwide standard for designing sustainable Blockchain / DLT systems and for assessing and monitoring the environmental footprint (electric consumption, carbon footprint / CO₂ emission, water footprint, electronic waste, land footprint) of Blockchain / DLT systems (on-going works at ISO/TC307/WG3, WG6 and WG8) and a European standard covering the European specificities (on-going work at CEN-CENELEC/JTC19/WG2)

Challenge: The high carbon footprint of blockchain technologies due to their intensive energy consumption (RAND Analysis).

Solution: Develop and implement more energy-efficient solutions and promote the use of renewable energy in blockchain operations.

Data protection, security, privacy, GDPR

Security and Privacy:

Challenge: Maintaining the security and privacy of data on blockchain platforms remains a critical issue (RAND Analysis).

Solution: Enhance security and privacy mechanisms by adopting robust standards and implementing advanced encryption and authentication technologies.

Data deletion, selective disclosure of anonymous non-transferable credentials

Artificial Intelligence and blockchain (e.g. governance and transparency layer on DLT)

AI and BC

Various standardisation topics

common terminology

In the short term, it's necessary to focus on elementary technical solutions on top of blockchain/DLT with requirements analysis. After that, the integration of other technologies such as AI is important. Finally, in the long term, globally interoperable solutions with sustainability support should be addressed.

1) creating appetite and demand for security defense layer solution of the peer-to-peer protocol by leading with reference architecture of p2p ingress and egress on layer 0 /peer to peer communication layer of blockchain architecture.

2) Standards created must be covering at least 4 major DLT protocols and all combinations of public private and permissioned use cases.

3) link open source security efforts separate to core smart contract /DLT code /function logic. Or create a standard covering only those oss risks

Specifically, there needs to be standards in place for automatically identifying people, machines and organisation and for exchanging data between these in a trusted way.

Additional suggestions regarding policy measures and the legal framework

Challenge: The lack of clarity and uniformity in blockchain regulations and standards, including uncertainty regarding the legal validity of electronic signatures and digital documents, (Trade Finance Global), (RAND Analysis).

Solution: Implement coherent global regulations and establish uniform standards that address data security, privacy, and governance. Initiatives like the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) and the UNCITRAL Model Law on Electronic Transferable Records are steps in this direction.

Challenge: Legal recognition of digital transactions and electronic documents is not uniform across countries, hindering the seamless operation of blockchain solutions (Trade Finance Global).

Solution: Adopt and harmonize legal frameworks, like the UNCITRAL Model Law, to provide a consistent basis for the use of electronic transferable records both domestically and internationally.

Legal enforceability of smart contracts

As Trusted leader are included within eIDAS review, implementing acts need to refer to standards....

Public Awareness and Education:

Challenge: Limited understanding and awareness of blockchain technology among businesses and the general public, (Deloitte United States).

Solution: Increase public awareness and education initiatives to inform stakeholders about the potential benefits and applications of blockchain technology.

Technical Maturity:

Challenge: The perceived immaturity of blockchain technology and the associated risks of early adoption, (RAND Analysis).

Solution: Invest in research and development to mature blockchain technology, reduce associated risks, and demonstrate its reliability and effectiveness through pilot projects and real-world applications.

Business Models and Use Cases:

Challenge: Insufficient evidence on business gains and the broader economic impact of blockchain technology, (RAND Analysis).

Solution: Develop and document successful use cases and business models that clearly demonstrate the economic benefits and efficiency gains from blockchain adoption.

By addressing these challenges and leveraging the outlined opportunities, the blockchain and DLT ecosystem can achieve broader adoption and deliver its full potential across various sectors.

Specific recommendations related to identification & trusted services

Needs
A European standard framework for blockchain / DLT solutions for EU Digital Identity Wallet (EUDIW)
EU EBSI
EU-wide identity and wallet management may be necessary for healthcare, financial and further transactions across Europe and worldwide.
Qualified Electronic Ledger Certification process and guidelines
Signature standards on blockchains and standards for oracles.
This one of the major objectives for Decentralized PKI (DPKI) standardization activity.
transform it into a standard
trust services
Trusted ledgers are included (as well as e-Archives)
Additional comments
Don't know, but I am not aware of widely accepted standards
Electronic ledgers are not yet standardized
To support trust services, identification is a very essential component.
Necessary for broader adoption.
Fundamental
Identity is not well understood and esp. its management

Specific recommendations related to Decentralised Identifiers (DIDs)

Needs
A worldwide standard bridging Decentralised Identifier / Identity and Blockchain / DLT & a European one covering the European specificities including eIDAS2
format, resolution, DID policies
Interoperability between competing standards.
interoperability standards
Correlation to accounts, vaults and other high-level structures through correct use of identities
Distributed identity
It could be interesting to explore how DPKI could support DIDs. It is clear that there is a relationship.
later
One standard to harmonize the DID registries could be useful
The identifiers should enable decentralized verifiable digital identity to improve security of blockchain solutions
To ensure provenance and trust for dPKI model
To identify people, machines, sensors and organisations in smart contracts/reporting and for machine economy.
Additional comments
Don't know, but I am not aware of widely accepted standards
Necessary particularly for auditing purposes.
Solutions for decentralized Internet require DIDs.

Specific recommendations related to data exchange

Needs
data exchange protocols
Data formats developed specifically for DLT
Data formats.
data structures
eIDAS2
Literally any
more interchain standards
Official formats based on common technologies out there for easy exchange of data between various stakeholders.
Public-key infrastructure is the bases for secure data exchange. A PKI based on blockchain as DPKI will provide global support.
Receiving assets/tokens on public address
standard/regulation to accept public blockchains
Possible solutions
ISO/TC307/WG6 has published ISO/TR 6277 in Feb. 2024 about data flow models for Blockchain / DLT that should cover the need in first approach
Additional comments
Data is important form several viewpoints - not least national security. Being clear of rules for safe data exchange is important.
Cross-Infrastructure communication and data exchange are crucial for long-term sustainable blockchain solutions
Necessary to improve cross-border transfers.
Please code this as "maybe". I lack the expertise to comment on the current DLT situation, but can say that unless data exchange is easy, prospects for DLT seem low.
Privacy preserving data exchange is essential.

Specific recommendations related to the CO₂ footprint

Needs
Electronic ledgers in eIDAS2 have to be eco-sustainable and there are no standards to define what this means
Ensure real CO ₂ parameters are applied
Environmental footprint to be addressed more broadly: electric consumption, carbon footprint / CO ₂ emission, water footprint, electronic waste, land footprint
standards to calculate CO ₂ footprint of each transaction
Energy consumption
Possible solutions
Definitely, TC307/AG1 (I am convenor) is developing proposals for the TC's Strategic Business plan right now.
Need to have consistent measurements to begin with - what is measured and how. Then regulation of what CO ₂ footprint is acceptable and how to force internalization of cost.
some regulation on max CO ₂ footprint per block registered on the ledger. As the cost is incremental, sharding and other techniques should be enforced
Certain BC architectures (proof of work), I understand, are extremely compute-intensive. This needs to be restricted & the CO ₂ implications addressed, both for acceptability of DLT and for planetary reasons.
Additional comments
Energy efficiency of blockchain solutions should be monitored and reported to improve development in this direction
It's necessary to develop lightweight blockchain/DLT.
Propose standard which are accepted and used by Industry
Use of electricity is an important aspect requiring compact encoding and efficient processing of the consensus process. Bitcoin is a bad example.
Cannot use e.g. Bitcoin and computation intense technologies.
less PoW

Specific recommendations related to data protection and the GDPR

Recommendations
Clarify if a public key is personal data (and it's better if it's not)
GDPR: recommendation not to store personal data on Layer 1 blockchain / DLT; need for standardisation recommendations about "erasable" Layer 2 solutions
The DPKI project includes capabilities for identity management and access control, which is important for GDPR.
The EU needs a blockchain-based identity system. Any 'centralised' system run by government or industry-such as the Canadian banking model-will degrade quickly over time. It needs to start as a decentralised system, with safeguards to maintain consensus
The hash/encrypted version/ZKP of personal data is personal data? IP addresses are personal data, and hashes are even better identifiers... In a permissionless blockchain, it is not possible to identify data processors.
The right to be forgotten
the right to be forgotten
to clearly specify the use and policy for pseudonym identifiers
Understanding the basic question of where blockchain/DLT plays its role in GDPR.
which HASH calculation procedures are accepted under GDPR?
Possible solutions
There are some standards on blockchain based data sharing and exchange in ITU-T
https://www.europarl.europa.eu/RegData/etudes/STUD/2019/634445/EPRS_STU(2019)634445(ANN1)_EN.pdf https://www.europarl.europa.eu/RegData/etudes/STUD/2019/634445/EPRS_STU(2019)634445_EN.pdf
Additional comments
It depends whether GDPR-related data should be stored in blockchain or not. Preferably, all private GDPR-related data should be stored off-chain, however, this might be different for different cases.
GDPR is a big thing in Europe, outside of the EU the blockchain community is far less sensitive to personal data issues.

Specific recommendations related to AI

Recommendations
AI fakes will require use of blockchain assurance mechanisms.
It might be necessary in the near future when AI solutions become widely applied in the industry. For blockchain-AI solutions standardization will also become necessary. Certain AI-generated or AI-modified data might be stored in blockchain, etc.
common AI and BC systems
Additional comments
Although there are no relevant efforts for now, for governance by technology (DLT, blockchain), AI will be quite essential.
Academic literature puts forward the benefits of blockchain & AI solutions for UN SDGs whereas no discussion exists between ISO/TC307 & JTC1/SC42 about it
Again, regulations would not sort anything by settings standards directly, but setting the framework for voluntary standards and providing benchmarks is a noble aim.

Suggestions for additional regulatory/policy support

Suggestions for additional regulatory/policy support for blockchain/DLT technologies
A commitment by the EU to support decentralised solutions and avoid centralising to rely on one state or small group of states
Case-specific implementations might need certain policy support to enable and motivate industrial and societal support and engagement. For instance, DLT solutions for the food industry and food provenance as well as food waste tracking are necessary but lack policy support for a wide adoption.
Code efficiency
EU Copyright Directive: would gain being reopened with Blockchain / DLT supporting the automation of copyright & neighbouring rights management.
eu-wide cryptocurrency taxes
the right to be forgotten
Additional comments
In my view predictability on how and under what conditions the current rules may change, would be a great help for DLT standardization
Foundations: what is a DLT? Is a network of 200 nodes managed by a single entity a reliable DLT? When a DLT is sufficiently resilient? Scope: when a DLT makes sense and when it is only a dangerous technology? Accountability in some blockchains may be not straightforward due to privacy preserving technology, the dynamic nature of the network, the dangers of economic incentives as the only reason not to misbehave (small networks are really fragile and successfully hacked and attacked multiple times without anyone raising warnings on this. Even the Bitcoin network may collapse if the economic growth does not compensate for the block reward halving).